

Research of Aviation PM Technologies, mOdelling and Regulation - RAPTOR

Clean Sky 2 JU under H2020 Grant Agreement number: 863969

D5.1

Emission and Dispersion Modelling Review

Delivery Date:	2021-08-31 (M22)
Date of submission:	2021-10-12

Start date of project:	2019-11-01
Duration:	24 months + 6

LEAD BENEFICIARY FOR THIS DELIVERABLE

Name:	Janicke Consulting
Contact Person:	Dr Ulf Janicke
Address:	Hermann-Hoch-Weg 1, 88662 Überlingen, Germany
Phone:	+49 (0)7551 947 1818
E-mail:	uj@janicke.de

AUTHORS

Participants:	Anet, Julien; Bertier, Nicolas; Cremaschi, Michele; Dellaert, Stijn; Edebeli, Jacinta; Huck, Violaine; Janicke, Ulf; Kuenen, Jeroen; Lim, Ling; Terrenoire, Etienne		
Work Package:	WP5		
Dissemination level:	Public	Nature:	Report
Version:	0.17	Number of Pages:	63

REVISION HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR / REVIEWER	NOTES
0.17	2021-10-12	UJ	Submission

REVIEWED AND SIGNED OFF BY

ROLE	DATE	NAME	SIGNATURE
DELIVERABLE LEADER	2021-10-12	Dr Ulf Janicke	
WP LEADER	2021-10-12	Dr Ulf Janicke	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document contains an overview, based on about 150 cited references, of published research activities related to particulate matter emission in the context of aviation. It covers emissions, dispersion modelling, and regulations. Some focus is set on intra-engine processes and on emissions beyond CAEP, in particular, from non-regulated engines.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS	3
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	5
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Emission.....	8
2.1 Intra-engine processes	8
2.1.1 Some elements of aeronautical engines and combustion chambers.....	10
2.1.2 Soot modelling in the combustion chamber.....	13
2.1.3 From the combustion chamber to the engine exhaust	17
2.1.4 Outlook.....	18
2.2 Regulated engines	18
2.2.1 General introduction	18
2.2.2 Related publications and main results	19
2.2.3 Outlook.....	21
2.3 Non-regulated engines.....	21
2.3.1 General introduction	21
2.3.2 Emission profiles of non-regulated engines.....	22
2.3.3 Outlook.....	28
2.4 Volatile particulate matter	29
2.5 Emission inventories	30
2.5.1 Airport level (single airport)	30
2.5.2 Regional level (Country, District).....	31
2.5.3 Global level.....	36
3 Dispersion modelling.....	37
3.1 Airport level.....	38
3.2 Regional/Global level	39
3.2.1 Dynamical approach.....	39
3.2.2 Physico-chemical approach.....	40
3.2.3 Inter-comparison study	43
3.3 Exhaust dynamics	44
3.4 Particulate matter transformation.....	45
4 Regulation	46
4.1 Emissions	46
4.1.1 Aircraft related emissions: ICAO engine emissions regulation	46
4.1.2 Non-Aircraft related emissions: European regulations.....	48
4.2 Ambient concentration	49
4.2.1 EU directives and WHO recommendations.....	49

4.3	Indoor and workplace	50
4.3.1	Workplace	50
4.3.2	Indoor air quality	51
4.4	Outlook.....	52
5	Literature.....	53

This project has received funding from the Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research program under grant agreement No 863969

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

A/B	After Burn
AEDT	Aviation Environmental Design Tool
APU	Auxiliary Power Unit
BC	Black Carbon
CAEP	Committee for Aviation and Environmental Protection
CCD	Climb, Cruise, Decent
CDSM	Chemical Discrete Sectional Method
CLRTAP	Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution
CO	Carbon Monoxide
CTM	Chemistry Transport Model
CRM	Climate Regional Model
DAC	Dual Annular Combustor
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt
DQMOM	Direct Quadrature Method of Moments
DSM	Discrete Sectional Method
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	Elemental Carbon
EEA	European Environment Agency
EEDB	Engine Emissions Databank
EEP	Engine Exit Plane
EI	Emission Index
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme
EU	European Union
FDR	Flight Data Recorder
FOA	First Order Approximation
FOCA	Federal Office of Civil Aviation (Switzerland)
GMD	Geometric Mean Diameter
GSD	Geometric Standard Deviation
GSE	Ground Support Equipment
HP	High Pressure
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organisation
IFR	Instrument Flight Rules
ISA	International Standard Atmosphere
kN	kilo Newton
LDPS	Lagrangian Discrete Particle Simulation
LES	Large-Eddy Simulation
LP	Low Pressure
LTO	Landing/Take-Off cycle
MC	Monte-Carlo method
MOM	Method Of Moments
MOMIC	Method Of Moments with Interpolative Closure
NDF	Number Density Function
NO _x	Nitrogen Oxides
nvPM	non-volatile Particulate Matter
OC	Organic Carbon

PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon
PBE	Population Balance Equation
PM	Particulate Matter (vPM plus nvPM)
PN	Particle Number
PSD	Particle Size Density
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
RQL	Rich Burn, Quick-Mix, Lean Burn
SCOPE11	Smoke Correlation for Particle Emissions - CAEP11
SMPS	Scanning Mobility Particle Sizer
SO ₂	Sulphur Dioxide
TAPS	Twin Annular Premixing Swirler
TC	Total Carbon
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
UHC	Unburned HydroCarbon
VFR	Visual Flight Rules
vPM	volatile Particulate Matter
WHO	World Health Organisation

1 Introduction

The Seventh Environment Action Programme of the European Union (EU), *“Living well, within the limits of our planet”* (EEA, 2013), recognises that the long-term EU goals to achieve are *“... levels of air quality that do not give rise to significant negative impacts on, and risks to, human health and the environment”*. In addition, the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (UN, 2015) have been defined to *“... ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all; and make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable”*.

Air pollution contributes to serious illness such as heart disease, respiratory problems, and cancer. The European Environment Agency estimates that air pollution (specifically PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and O₃) was responsible for more than 500,000 premature deaths in EU28 countries in 2014 and in excess of 530,000 across Europe, where particulate matter (PM) with aerodynamic diameters below 2.5 µm (PM_{2.5}) is estimated to account for 80% of the premature deaths (EEA, 2017).

PM is characterised by different physical and chemical properties, such as size distribution, morphological structure, and chemical composition. There is significant uncertainty how PM species and precursors evolve within the atmosphere, and which parameters of PM are the most relevant ones in the context of human health. It is considered that ultrafine particles (UFP, PM with an aerodynamic diameter below 0.1 µm) may have greater toxicity on an equal mass basis than currently regulated larger particles (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), mainly because of their larger number concentration and their larger surface area, which is a potentially important toxicological interface. In addition, smaller particles can penetrate deeper the lung, and inhalation of UFP can lead to deposition onto the regional epithelia of the respiratory tract.

Aircraft engines are a relevant source of UFP. The particles are emitted in primary form as non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM), mainly in form of soot. In course of atmospheric transport, nucleation and growth of precursor gases such as organic gases, nitrates and sulphates (volatile and semi-volatile PM) can substantially increase the number of UFP in the exhaust plume. Studies (Habre et al., 2018; Hofman et al., 2016; Hudda and Fruin, 2016; Keuken et al., 2015) indicate that the contribution of aircraft operations to ambient UFP concentration at and around airports can be significant.

Concern regarding air quality in and around airports has been recognised by The Advisory Council for Aviation Research and Innovation in Europe (ACARE). In Action Area 3.5, ACARE identifies the need for airport development to be sustainable, stating *“assessment of air quality impact at or near airports must be based on accurate measures or prediction of air vehicle emissions combined with sound atmospheric transport models”*. These challenges, which are further addressed within Flightpath 2050 (EC, 2011), amplify the requirement for an enhanced qualitative, quantitative and holistic understanding of aircraft engine emissions.

For the certification of aircraft engines with a rated thrust greater than 26.7 kN, only the so-called smoke number (SN), a measure of the blackening of a filter material, was used until a few years ago. At the 10th meeting of CAEP/ICAO (Committee on Aviation Environmental

Protection of the International Civil Aviation Organisation), a certification standard for the mass of non-volatile ultrafine particles was agreed (nvPM, valid from January 1, 2020), which also requires their number to be specified. Standard methods for measuring mass and number emissions were developed and established. At the 11th CAEP meeting in early 2019, emission limits for both mass and number of nvPM were agreed upon (effective January 1, 2023).

Effects of engine properties, ambient conditions, and fuel composition on effective UFP emissions are presently not fully understood. Furthermore, the regulations of ICAO/CAEP do neither address the effects on the global atmosphere by excluding cruise conditions nor the contribution of nvPM which is emitted by smaller engines and engines rated on shaft speed. These factors need to be considered for a European roadmap for improving current nvPM methodologies and future nvPM measurement technologies and regulation beyond CAEP.

This review provides an introduction and an overview of PM aircraft emissions, its atmospheric dispersion, modelling approaches, regulations, and health effects, where some focus is given to more specific aspects and to issues that are beyond CAEP. The main goal of this report is to provide the current state-of-the-art with regard to aircraft PM emissions and related atmospheric dispersion, as well as to identify main gaps in the current knowledge that should be targeted in future research.

Section 2 provides an overview of PM emissions from aircraft. It contains an elaborated overview of intra-engine processes and of emissions from non-regulated engines. In addition, it covers regulated engines and aspects of volatile particles and emission inventories. Section 3 gives an overview of aircraft-related dispersion modelling, and Section 4 an overview of regulations in the context of PM.

Information on toxicology and health effects of ultrafine particles from aircraft engines is not addressed as there is another Deliverable (6.1) of this project that is dedicated to this issue.

2 Emission

2.1 Intra-engine processes

Aircraft emissions are composed of greenhouse gases (CO₂, water vapor), NO_x (NO and NO₂), unburned hydrocarbons (UHC), CO, Sulphur Oxides (SO_x) and PM. These emissions impact both the air quality, especially at and around airports, and the climate. To limit the emission of these species, CAEP has established increasingly stringent norms, whose milestones are summarized in the Figure 2-1 below (see ICAO, (2014) for more details on evolution of standards and procedures for the emissions certification of aircraft engines).

Figure 2-1 CAEP35 milestones.

Thus, year after year, aviation’s environmental footprint per passenger-km has gradually decreased. However, there is still a long way to go to make aircraft neutral from the environmental and human health points of view.

Before going further in the analysis, it is worthwhile to detail the main characteristics of these aeronautical chemical emissions impact, from the point of view of air quality and climate:

- In the vicinity of airports, a pollutant of major concern used to be NO_x (sum of nitrogen dioxide, NO₂, and nitrogen monoxide, NO). NO_x in airport surroundings origins from several sources, in particular aircraft, ground services equipment and access road traffic. According to Liu et al. (2017), a significant portion of the NO_x is emitted outside the LTO cycle.

NO₂ and ozone (O₃) can result in health issues, such as airways inflammation and constriction. Like secondary PM from NO_x, primary non-volatile PM¹ (mainly soot particles) can have significant health impacts. According to Gauderman et al. (2004), exposure to PM in the polluted air correlates with adverse health effects, including cardiovascular, respiratory and allergic diseases, and damage to cellular proteins and DNA. Moreover, inhalation of organic compounds, such as organic coating on soot and polycyclic aromatic compounds, can result in reactions releasing free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) in the body. These reactive species can cause oxidative stress with implications on health.

¹ A "volatile" particle is one that, upon evaporation at elevated temperatures, does not leave a residual refractory core of sufficient size to be detected as a condensation nucleus, or CN; hence, a "nonvolatile" particle is one that contains a detectable solid core. (Yu and Turco, 1997)

- Concerning the impact of aircraft emission on climate, three main mechanisms increase the greenhouse effect. The first is CO₂ release to the atmosphere. Second are emissions of NO_x, which contribute to upper tropospheric O₃ formation; surface O₃ concentrations have both regional and local implications. Third, there are contrails. The radiative forcing of contrails depends on the evolution of the characteristics of ice crystal distribution, including number concentration, the size and the shape, within the plume.

Emitted soot particles influence contrail formation and cirrus clouds optical properties. Soot particles are generally hydrophobic and require activation by the addition of some other hygroscopic substance, such as H₂SO₄ and chemi-ions (emitted alongside soot) to influence contrail formation (Kärcher and Yu, 2009).

Therefore, NO_x, SO_x, and PM negatively impact both human health and climate. The topic of NO_x being particularly crucial, it has been the subject of numerous works and its modelling in combustion chambers is now fairly well understood. This is also because NO_x is involved in relatively few chemical reactions. However, this is not the case with soot, which are solid carbon particles, involved in several complex physicochemical processes. In addition, for both health and environmental issues, it is not sufficient to focus only on the soot concentration. Indeed, soot particle size as well as its morphology and surface reactivity are important parameters.

As a result, in the next subsections of this chapter, a focus is set on soot modelling, with emphasis on the most recent and promising approaches. Another rather poorly understood subject is the evolution of the chemical species between the combustion chamber, where they are created, and the output of the engine. This important topic (the quantities of real interest for health and climate being those measured at the engine exhaust, and not in the combustion chamber) will also be discussed below. As a starting point, the main characteristics of aeronautical combustion chambers are explained to provide the necessary context for further discussions.

2.1.1 Some elements of aeronautical engines and combustion chambers

2.1.1.1 Turbofan architecture

Figure 2-2 presents a generic representation of the architecture of the core of a turbofan engine. The fan takes in the incoming air, which passes through the engine core or a bypass section; a larger fraction of intake air bypasses the engine core. In the engine core, air pressure is increased by compressor stages (low pressure, LP, then high pressure, HP). Air flow then enters the combustion chamber (or "burner"), where it is mixed with fuel, which is successively injected, atomized, and vaporized. The air/fuel mixture then burns, while releasing, in form of heat, the chemical energy stored in the chemical bonds of the fuel.

Figure 2-2 Sketch of a jet engine. Picture from Jeff Dahl, distributed under CC BY-SA 4.0 and download from Wikimedia.

Hot combustion products enter turbine stages (high pressure, then low pressure) that will in turn drive the compressor stage. At last, hot gases are accelerated through the nozzle, providing thrust to the engine. All aircraft chemical emissions are issued from the combustion chamber. However, chemical species created in the combustion chamber continue to react in the hot section (in particular, across the HP turbine), which could potentially significantly vary their concentration between the burner and the exhaust of the engine.

2.1.1.2 Pollutant formation in the combustion chamber

This section focuses on the main mechanisms involved in the formation of chemical species and particles in the combustion chamber. The mechanisms presented below are fairly general and occur in all types of combustion chambers (RQL, TAPS, DAC, etc.). Large parts of this section are based on summaries by Liu et al. (2017):

- **NO_x:** NO_x includes NO and NO₂. There are several sources of NO in the combustion chamber (fuel NO, prompt NO, thermal NO). The thermal NO is the predominant source of NO in practical gas turbine combustors. This NO is produced where the flame temperature is greater than 1800 K as in the post flame region. As a rule of thumb, thermal NO emission doubles every 100 K from 1800 K onwards.
- **CO:** CO is produced when inefficient combustion occurs. Conditions such as low temperature, low pressure, and low global equivalence ratio, as in low power modes, promote CO formation. There may also exist a freezing process near the cooled walls, which can stop the CO to CO₂ conversion and therefore, lead to CO emissions at the chamber exit. In addition, high temperatures (above 1800 K) at stoichiometric fuel-air mixture can promote CO₂ dissociation leading to CO formation.
- **UHC:** Unburned hydrocarbons (UHCs) are produced due to incomplete combustion. Similar conditions (except the high temperature splitting of CO₂) promoting CO production also lead to UHC emission. In addition, poor fuel atomization can result in liquid fuel clusters, leading to incomplete combustion and UHC emission.
- **SO_x:** Sulphur oxides (SO_x) are formed from the oxidation of the sulphur content of jet fuel by oxygen during combustion. This is especially the case with conventional jet fuel. Alternative fuels are being developed which have little to no sulphur content

- Soot: Soot or smoke is produced in regions where there is inadequate mixing of fuel and air leading to fuel-rich regions in the combustion chamber. Like CO and UHC, in addition to fuel/air mixing quality, equivalence ratio, pressure, and the quality of fuel atomization affect soot formation.

2.1.1.3 Combustion chamber technologies

In this section, a focus is set on two chamber technologies: the most widespread Rich Burn, Quick-Mix, Lean Burn (RQL) and the more recent Twin Annular Premixing Swirler (TAPS) systems. Most of the information given on these systems come from Liu et al. (2017), Stickle and Barrett (2014), and Bergthorson and Thomson (2015).

2.1.1.3.1 RQL technologies

RQL chambers were developed with the main objective of reducing NO_x emissions compared to former generations. To achieve this, combustion starts in a fuel-rich area (yellow part in Figure 2-3), whose relatively low temperature and low oxygen content limit NO_x formation. Flow exiting this rich zone is then quickly diluted. Consequently, the time spent in the stoichiometric area, which is the most favourable for the NO_x formation, is very short. Flow exiting the chamber is a uniform lean mixture, which preserves turbine blades (turbine blade lifespan is very sensitive to temperature levels). Regarding the stabilization mechanism of the turbulent flame, the fuel is injected in a swirl motion, generating a large recirculating area in the chamber; this allows the flame to be anchored.

Compared to previous generation combustion chambers, RQL technologies have significantly reduced NO_x emissions. Nevertheless, it is somewhat difficult to control soot, CO, and UHC emissions. Furthermore, it is technologically difficult to cool the primary zone walls (no direct injection of air; double wall principle is often used in practice).

Figure 2-3 Sketch of RQL combustion chamber, from Bergthorson and Thomson (2015).

2.1.1.3.2 TAPS combustor

TAPS chambers were developed, like RQL chambers, to minimize NO_x emissions. The main idea behind the concept of TAPS chambers is mostly to operate in a lean premixed combustion regime, which limits CO, UHC, and soot emissions. However, this type of combustion may lead to very unstable regimes (with the risk of flashback) and must be stabilized. Stabilization is achieved by a central pilot injection which is particularly useful at low engine power. Like RQL combustors, swirl injection is used to anchor the flame.

To compare with the RQL system, the flow structure in a combustion chamber equipped with a TAPS system is shown in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4 Sketch of TAPS combustion chamber, from Bergthorson and Thomson, (2015).

TAPS combustor development started in engines that entered service in 2010. LEAP engines (Airbus A320 NEO, Boeing 737 Max and COMAC 919) are equipped with this technology.

2.1.2 Soot modelling in the combustion chamber

2.1.2.1 Major topics and main physical mechanisms

2.1.2.1.1 Main characteristics

Aeronautical soot emissions cause both air quality and environmental problems, but there are also other effects specific to the combustion chamber. Inside the burner, soot radiative emissions are concentrated in visible and infrared wavelengths (sooting flames are bright and yellowish), which increases the thermal load on the walls. Therefore, soot may also locally modify the temperature field (Dorey et al., 2011), with indirect consequence on the formation of other pollutants, such as NO_x whose formation is particularly sensitive to temperature.

The main characteristics of aeronautical soot as well as the evolution mechanisms inside the burner are discussed in more detail in the following. Soot has a complex structure, which can be divided into several levels from crystallite nanostructure to large aggregates. In the context of this work, the focus is on the following levels:

- Near-spherical primary particles, with diameters between 10 nm and 80 nm and composed of about 104 crystallite structures.
- Soot aggregate with fractal-like shape, composed of several thousands of primary particles and whose characteristic dimension is about several micrometres.

2.1.2.1.2 Overview of main mechanisms involved in soot formation and evolution

The main steps involved in the formation of soot are illustrated in Figure 2-5.

Figure 2-5 Soot formation and oxidation, courtesy of Nicolas Dellinger, ONERA.

Surface growth and condensation lead to increase in total soot mass, while coagulation affects the number of soot particles and the particle size. Globally, the following fundamental stages are involved in soot's life:

- Nucleation of solid carbon particles from gaseous species, the heaviest of which are the Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs).
- Mass growth, including surface growth, condensation, and coagulation.
- Oxidation, mainly by O_2 and by OH radicals.

Each of these steps is detailed hereinafter, relying on recent comprehensive reviews of these physical mechanisms (Gallen, 2020; Rodrigues, 2018).

2.1.2.1.2.1 Soot precursor formation

A soot particle is a solid carbon particle, whose inception is due to chemical reactions between gaseous molecules issued from fuel decomposition reactions. Among these molecules, PAHs play a particularly crucial role. Note that the well-known benzene aromatic molecule, C_6H_6 , composed of a single ring (A1), constitutes the first link of these heavy PAHs. There are still a lot of uncertainties about the processes that lead to PAH formation, which explains why there are so many different models in literature. However, the most widely used mechanism remains the H-Abstraction- C_2H_2 -Addition (HACA) mechanism, proposed by Frenklach et al. (1985). This mechanism is based on a two-step pattern: the abstraction of a hydrogen atom forming a radical, and then the addition of acetylene on the radical site.

2.1.2.1.2.2 Soot nucleation

Soot nucleation is the step allowing the transition from the gas to the solid phase. Several pathways for soot nucleation have been suggested (Wang, 2010):

- PAH dimerization: formation of PAH dimers is explained by PAHs collision (Frenklach and Wang, 1991) ;
- PAH addition: chemical growth of potential soot from addition of PAHs.

2.1.2.1.2.3 Soot growth

Once soot particles are formed by nucleation, the total amount of soot is mainly influenced by soot growth (Haynes and Wagner, 1982) through three main processes:

- Surface growth: This involves the adsorption of gaseous species like acetylene to the soot particle surface (Harris and Weiner, 1983). An analogy between HACA processes at PAH and soot surface was proposed by Frenklach and Wang (1994) and is now widely used. Numerous extensions to HACA mechanism have been proposed to extend its validity since the first formulation (Mauss et al., 1994; Pitsch, 1996; Wang et al., 1996; Frenklach and Warnatz, 1987; M. E. Mueller et al., 2009a) . A major topic in surface growth modelling is how to account for the soot surface reactivity.
- Condensation: This is equivalent to the collision of a soot particle with a PAH, increasing its size. Saffaripour et al. (2014) have observed that the ratio between nucleation and condensation collisional efficiencies strongly affects soot primary particle diameter (the smaller the ratio, the larger the primary particle diameter).
- Coagulation: This represents the collision between soot particles. This process increases the particles size, leaving total mass unchanged. Soot morphology is closely related to interactions between particles. There are two coagulation processes: coalescent growth and agglomeration. In the case of coalescent growth, particles collide and merge forming a larger and spherical particle (Wang, 2010). Coalescence can be compared to the collision of liquid droplets (Dobbins, 2002) and occurs typically for nascent particles with liquid-like behaviour (Abid et al., 2008; Zhao et al., 2007; Barone et al., 2003). In the case of agglomeration, up on collision, soot particles stick together at the point of contact creating fractal-like structures. This process involves mostly older and bigger particles (Sgro et al., 2009).

2.1.2.1.2.4 Soot oxidation and fragmentation

The main oxidizing molecules in combustion chambers are primarily O₂ and OH with minor contributions from other molecules containing oxygen (like H₂O, CO₂, NO₂) or atomic oxygen (Cavaliere et al., 1994).

2.1.2.2 Overview of the different available models

2.1.2.2.1 Empirical and semi-empirical models

Empirical models are based on experimental measurements. These models apply fuel and combustion properties in calculating soot concentration and size distribution (Moss, 1994; Magnussen and Hjertager, 1977; Legros and Torero, 2015). Empirical models, for soot

formation in this case, may be suitable for larger scale predictions, but without increase in complexity of input, these models become weak predictors of a wide range of soot properties.

Semi-empirical models, like that of Leung et al. (1991), have added complexity in input parameters to improve model predictability. These models combine measurement data and descriptions of processes involved in the process of interest. In the case of soot formation, simple descriptions of soot formation, growth and destruction processes are included in the model. Increase in the complexity of process description may increase the predictive power of the model (Dorey et al., 2011).

2.1.2.2.2 Detailed dispersed phase models

Since soot particles are very small, their dynamic and thermal characteristic times are very short compared to those of the flow; this results in Stokes numbers ("classical" Stokes number and thermal Stokes number) much lower than unity. In other words, soot particles can be viewed as tracers embedded in the gas flow, always in dynamic and thermal equilibrium with it. Therefore, velocity and temperature of the soot are always assumed to be equal to those of the flow, which constitutes a very convenient simplification for modelling, particularly with Eulerian approaches.

2.1.2.2.2.1 Eulerian models

Detailed models of soot include complex descriptions of both soot chemical kinetics and particle dynamics. In the chemical reactions scheme, soot formation and growth process as well as the destruction of soot or precursors through oxidation are often included (Kennedy, 1997). Such schemes quickly grow due to the need to account for intermediate species and their transitions (Wang and Frenklach, 1997).

Particle dynamics refers to the evolution of soot particle in size and number through the aforementioned processes. Particle dynamics have been modelled using sectional methods (Rodrigues et al., 2018) or method of moments (Frenklach and Wang, 1994; Mueller et al., 2009). Unlike empirical and semi-empirical models, these Eulerian approaches consider the polydispersity in size and the non-sphericity of the particles (Mueller et al., 2009; Eberle et al., 2017).

2.1.2.2.2.2 Lagrangian models

The Lagrangian tracking method is used like the Eulerian for calculating particle dynamics. Instead of looking at the particle in a fixed coordinate system, the Lagrangian method applies a coordinate system that moves with the particle. The evolution of the particle is described by its interactions with other gases and particles along its trajectory. The Lagrangian method can be computationally cost intensive. Therefore, efforts are made in the development of methods that reduce the computational demand by applying a hybrid Eulerian/Lagrangian approach (Dellinger et al., 2020). Figure 2-6 (simulations carried out with the ONERA CEDRE code) presents a simulation where such an Eulerian/Lagrangian approach showed promising results when compared to a real combustion chamber.

Figure 2-6 Simulation of the TLC configuration with Magnussen model, courtesy L.-H. Dorey, ONERA (left); Simulation of the FIRST configuration with a hybrid Eulerian/Lagrangian approach, courtesy N. Dellinger, ONERA (right).

2.1.3 From the combustion chamber to the engine exhaust

2.1.3.1 Context

As previously described, there is a very active research community working on the combustion chamber pollutant emissions modelling. However, the main interest in view of air quality and climate is not the pollutants formed in the burner, but what comes eventually out of the engine in the engine exhaust. This type of study is difficult to carry out from an experimental point of view (it is necessary to use a rig, integrating all the elements of the engine hot parts). There are very few studies published on this subject. Below is a summary of outcomes.

2.1.3.2 Brief review of conclusions on model developments

Bisson et al. (2016) present a zero-/one-dimensional gas turbine model for predicting gaseous aerosol precursors. With their model, which includes combustor and post combustor flow and a soot-dynamics model, the authors were able to observe significant evolutions of gas phase species post-combustion, especially sulphur species, which varied until the engine exit. Based on their observations, they concluded that their results on the stability of particulate matter emissions after the high pressure turbine pertain mostly to non-volatile particles.

Using one- and two-dimensional models, Lukachko et al. (1998) describe the formation and transformations of sulphate aerosol precursors in the exhaust, accounting for the effects of turbine, exhaust nozzle aerodynamics, and chemical kinetics. The authors observed significant influence of chemical transformation on sulphate aerosol precursors, much more than for NO_x species.

Nguyen et al. (2019) investigated SO_x and NO_x formation in an axial high-pressure turbine of aircraft engines with three-dimensional (3D) numerical simulations. They observed significant improvements in the prediction of SO_x and NO_x formation using 3D simulations compared to 1D or 2D approaches. They attributed this improvement to the ability of the 3D model to expand on the effect of spatial geometry on thermodynamics and chemical processes.

2.1.4 Outlook

For studies devoted to the impact of aeronautics on airports air quality or climate, it is of importance to have as input data an accurate description of the chemical properties of the emitted engine exhaust. Most unwanted chemical species are formed in the combustion chamber. While state-of-the-art models are reliable enough to predict NO_x and SO_x , the modelling of soot is a developing subject, which concentrates intense research activity. In addition to the volume fraction and the size distribution of soot particles, current challenges are the evolution of their morphology and surface reactivity.

To deal with these issues, Eulerian and Lagrangian methods along with detailed physical models have been developed. Latter approaches could play an increasingly important role in this topic in forthcoming years because they allow an increase in model complexity without significantly impacting computational cost. Concerning the evolution of unwanted species between the combustion chamber and the final engine exit, it seems that most of them evolve very little, with the notable exception of SO_x , which undergo deep transformations.

Finally, it should be mentioned that all the studies mentioned before were carried out in the framework of conventional jet fuel (kerosene-based) use. It seems clear that modifying the fuel composition could have a direct effect on engine emissions. For example, fuels with a very low aromatic and sulphur content – which potentially could reduce the levels of soot and sulphur oxides in a significant way – are being tested in laboratory settings. In the case of hydrogen use, the discussions on engine emissions would dramatically change with the removal of soot and sulphur oxides emissions. On the other hand, effects related to NO_x emissions and contrails would remain widely open.

2.2 Regulated engines

2.2.1 General introduction

Regulated aircraft engines are those required by ICAO to be certified for their emissions performance, namely turbofan and turbojet engines of maximum rated thrust ($\%F_{oo}$) greater than 26.7 kN (ICAO, 2017). Annex 16 Volume II to the *Convention on International Civil Aviation* contains the international standards for smoke, unburnt hydrocarbons, carbon monoxide, oxides of nitrogen and non-volatile Particulate Matter for regulated aircraft engines, as well as the respective test and measurement conditions to be followed.

Certification requirements include the need to report data under ISA conditions (except for the absolute humidity which is set to 0.00364 kg water/kg dry air), with a defined fuel specification and following specified test conditions requirements. As part of the engine certification requirements, engine manufacturers shall report the emissions data alongside some engine characteristics to ICAO. These data are stored and made publicly available through the ICAO Engine Emissions DataBank, EEDB (EEDB, 2021).

Emissions data of the regulated engines for the four power settings defined in the ICAO landing-take-off cycle (LTO cycle) are available in this database, referring to all operations the aircrafts carry out below 3,000 feet above field elevation. The power settings considered in the LTO cycle, relative to the maximum rated thrust of the engine at sea level (F_{oo}), include taxi/idle (7% F_{oo}), approach (30% F_{oo}), climb (85% F_{oo}), and take-off (100% F_{oo}). Moreover, a

typical time in each specific mode of operation is assigned to each phase of the LTO cycle: 26 min for idle, 4 min for approach, 2.2 min for climb, and 0.7 min for take-off. The present version of the databank is organised into 2 sheets: one including the data for gaseous and Smoke emissions and another one presenting the non-volatile PM emissions data (mass and number). NO_x, CO, HCs and engine smoke standards published by ICAO are provided in terms of total quantity of pollutants (Dp) emitted in an LTO cycle, divided by the sea level thrust (F₀₀) and plotted against the engine pressure ratio at maximum sea level thrust.

The application of the standards to the different aircraft engines varies depending on the considered species. In the case of subsonic engines, smoke standards apply to engines manufactured on or after 1 January 1983. For gaseous emissions, as indicated above, the standards apply to engines with rated output higher than 26.7 kN. For HC and CO, the starting date to consider the standards is 1 January 1986, while for NO_x, there are several stringency levels depending on the date of manufacture of the engine. Finally, for non-volatile PM emissions standards are applied to the in-production engines as of January 2020, with additional provisions starting on 1 January 2023. Turbofan and turbojets intended for supersonic speeds manufactured after 18 February 1982 must comply as well with smoke and gaseous pollutants standards as subsonic engines, even if data are measured in five different phases of the LTO cycle with slightly different values for the thrust and time in mode.

2.2.2 Related publications and main results

In this section, after having introduced the main characteristics of the aircraft regulated engines and their certification, an analysis of the main related publications and data sources is provided.

2.2.2.1 Emission indexes reported in the EEDB

Engine emissions reported in the EEDB for the four LTO phases must be reported under fixed thrust ratings and atmospheric conditions. As mentioned in ICAO document 9889 (2020), real operations are usually more complex than the four phases assumed at constant thrust rating. This is due to several operational reasons, the respective atmospheric conditions, and the fact that certification emissions are measured on uninstalled engines. All these factors contribute to the uncertainties of the emission indexes published in the EEDB. For this reason, the same document suggests that to obtain highly accurate results, more reliable data should be used, such as real data when possible.

Using certification data may result in an overestimation of certain pollutant emissions, as confirmed by a study conducted by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, which compared fuel burn and emissions in the LTO cycle for 12 different aircraft-engines (Chati and Balakrishnan, 2014). Working with certification data and operational (FDR) data converted to ISA conditions, the study found that in most of the cases, NO_x emission factors and fuel burn from certification data seem to be overestimated in the EEDB in all the phases of the LTO cycle. There were also some cases where the real emission index was higher than the certification value, such as in the case of the Boeing 777 during the take-off and climb-out phase

Factors that increase the uncertainties of the emission indices published in the EEDB are for example:

- The atmospheric conditions are considered to be ISA, while they vary widely in real time operations, resulting in modifications in the emitted pollutants.
- Full take-off thrust is considered in certification. However, reduced thrust is often applied for performance and cost-efficiency reasons. A study conducted at Heathrow airport (Koudis et al., 2017) using real data quantified the benefits in terms of pollutant emissions of using reduced take-off thrust instead of full thrust, as assumed by certification data. Results show that fuel consumption, NO_x and Black Carbon emissions are emitted in a significantly lower quantity applying reduced thrust, respectively 3.3%, 31.9% and 71.3% compared to full thrust. It is also mentioned that the minimum fuel consumption does not occur at the observed minimum thrust setting.
- Thrust at each phase is assumed to be constant in the certification LTO.
- In real aircraft operations, thrust is not constant over a LTO segment but acceleration and deceleration of the engines or stop-and-go situations occur. This is produced for example by congestion on taxiways and is known to lead to increases in fuel consumption and emissions (Moore et al., 2017).
- Use of reverse thrust during landing (Masiol and Harrison, 2014).
- Other factors such as pilots' behaviours, airlines operating procedures can influence the fuel flows; these are not considered in the certification process. However, as mentioned by Chati and Balakrishnan (2014), it is difficult to calculate the effect of each factor separately.
- Engine aging: According to ICAO document 9889, manufacturers design their products to be optimal at delivery, while performances could degrade over time for several reasons. The same document states that the effect of deterioration could contribute to an increase up to 3% of fuel and NO_x emissions at the LTO cycle, while there is no evidence that this affects CO and HC emissions. It is also mentioned that, for some engines, it was proven that deterioration affects nvPM emissions as well, but further studies are needed to confirm this finding.

2.2.2.2 Certification time for each LTO phase

An important factor to consider in the certification process is that the time-in-mode is assumed to be constant. However, there is evidence that these values may not be representative of real operations. In particular, the taxi time, which is the sum of the taxi-in and taxi-out phases, seems to be overestimated for a vast majority of airports. In fact, taxi time published in the publicly available data from Eurocontrol CODA 2019 database (EUROCONTROL, 2019²) for 487 airports in the world suggests that the taxi time (taxi-in plus taxi-out) in IATA summer period is, on average, around 17 minutes and 40 seconds, with about 12 minutes for taxi-out and about 5 minutes and 40 seconds for taxi-in. Of these 487 airports, only 58 (or 12% of the total) have an average taxi-in plus taxi-out time equal to or higher than

² <https://www.eurocontrol.int/publication/taxi-times-summer-2019>

26 minutes. If only EU airports are considered, this percentage drops to 1%, and the average to 14 minutes, with only Madrid Barajas and Dublin exceeding 26 minutes.

However, considering the busiest European airports, Paris Charles de Gaulle, Amsterdam Schiphol and Frankfurt, the average is above 23 minutes. This suggests that in busy airports with complex runway systems the average taxi time could be similar to the certification taxi time. Therefore, calculating total taxi emissions using the certification EIs and time in mode could lead to a significant overestimation of the real values, except for the airports with complex runway and taxiway systems.

Regarding the other phases of the LTO cycle, a study (Chati and Balakrishnan, 2014) compared for 12 flights the real time in mode with the ICAO certification time and found that for take-off all the analysed flights showed a value similar to the standard certification time. A similar situation was found for approach, but in 4 cases, all performed with wide body aircraft, the time-in-mode exceeded the certification time. In the case of climb-out, the real time seems to be much lower than the standard time in the majority of the cases.

2.2.3 Outlook

While the certification of engine emissions regulates the maximum amount of pollutant that an engine is allowed to emit in the LTO phase, assuring a reduction over time with the introduction of more stringent limits, the emission indices obtained in the certification processes might not be well representative of real operations for a variety of reasons. In particular, analyses comparing EEDB data with real data show how the certification fuel flows and emission indices have a tendency to overestimate if compared to real operations. In addition, the certification time assumed for each LTO phase, in particular for the taxi phase, seems to overestimate the time in real operations for most airports. Therefore, caution should be taken when using certification values to estimate engine emissions for a given aircraft. While there is extensive literature proving this concept for gaseous pollutants, for which certification data are available since decades, data on nvPM based on standardized measurements are relatively new (since EEDB Version 28 in 2020) and so far only available for selected engines.

2.3 Non-regulated engines

2.3.1 General introduction

ICAO requires that turbofan engines of maximum rated thrust at sea level (F_{00}) greater than 26.7 kN be certified for their emission performance (ICAO, 2017). As part of the certification requirement, engine manufactures shall report the emission data alongside some engine characteristics to ICAO. These data are stored and made publicly available in the ICAO engine emissions databank (EEDB, 2021). Therefore, for the turbofan engines that fall under this category, emission data for four power settings in the ICAO defined landing-take-off cycle (LTO cycle) are available. The LTO cycle includes taxi/idle at 7% F_{00} , Approach at 30% F_{00} , Climb at 85% F_{00} , and take-off at 100% F_{00} .

There are however other classes of engines that do not fall under this regulated category. These un- (or non-) regulated engines include small turbofan engines with rated thrust below 26.7 kN, military turbofan engines, auxiliary power units, turboprop engines, turboshaft

engines, piston (or reciprocating) engines. For these unregulated engines, there are limited publicly available data, exposing a major knowledge gap in aviation environmental impact assessment and mitigation. Here, we present a summary of available data with respect to the emission profiles and emission performance of unregulated engines. Unlike the regulated engines, available data in this case are often not reported according to the ICAO-prescribed LTO cycle. Emissions are primarily reported in pollutant units (grams or number of particles) per kilogram of fuel used, also known as emission indices (EIs), and/or concentrations in grams or number per volume of gas sampled.

A collection of the available data has been prepared as an Excel file with databank for unregulated engines, and a compilation of additional data tables.

2.3.2 Emission profiles of non-regulated engines

2.3.2.1 Non-regulated turbofan engines: small turbofan engines and military turbofan engines

Non-regulated small turbofan engines include engines with maximum rated thrust less than 26.7 kN. These engines are often used on business jets and small private jets. The military turbofan engines include certifiable turbofan engines used in military applications like fighter jets with an afterburn power or military mode. Therefore, one can expect that emission profiles may look like larger regulated turbofan engines (excluding the afterburn feature).

A major knowledge gap exists on the emissions from business and private jet engines as there is barely any publicly available emissions data. Klapmeyer and Marr (2012) present plume measurements, during regular airport operations, of nitrogen oxides (NO_x), carbon dioxide (CO₂), and particulate matter (PM) from Cessna C560 aircrafts carrying two Pratt & Whitney (PW) JTD15-5 engines during idle/taxi and at take-off. Durdina et al. (2019) reported the non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM) emissions from a Dassault FX 900Ex carrying three Honeywell TFE731-60 engines anchored on the tarmac at an airport for the LTO cycle defined by ICAO. In both studies, carbon monoxide and hydrocarbon emissions were not reported.

There are few reported emission data for this class of engines reported in the ICAO engine databank (EEDB, 2021). Pratt & Whitney has reported emissions from JT15D series (-1, -4, -5, -5A, -5B, -5C) and corrected as prescribed by ICAO. Like Pratt & Whitney, Allied Signal has reported emissions from TFE731-2-2B and TF3731-3 engines.

Klapmeyer and Marr (2012) observed higher NO_x emissions at take-off than at taxi/idle (Klapmeyer and Marr, 2012). This is the general case for turbofan engines, where NO_x emissions increase with increasing power due to increasing engine exhaust temperature at higher power. Observed field emission indices agreed with reported NO_x emission indices (EIs) in the ICAO database, also with higher NO_x at higher power (EEDB, 2021). In addition, carbon monoxide (CO) and unburned hydrocarbons (HC) for the reported JTD15 engines decreased with increase in power (ICAO, 2020). Klapmeyer and Marr (2012) also observed higher particle number emission at taxi/idle than at take-off. Smoke number (SN) in the EDB for these engines are limited, but indicate lower SN at lower power (EEDB, 2021).

Durdina et al. (2019) also observed maximum particle number (PN) emission at 7% of maximum thrust (taxi/idle). After 7% thrust, PN EIs decreased with increase in power. Therefore, like Klapmeyer and Marr (2012), taxi/idle PN emission was higher than at take-off;

nothing can be said with regard to a comparison at power settings between idle and take-off. Durdina et al. (2019) observed increase in particle geometric mean diameter (GMD) with increase in power. Smoke numbers were not reported for similar engines in the EEDB. Allied Signal-reported that CO and HC emissions decreased with increase in power, while NO_x increased with increase in power.

Military turbofan engines have slightly different power modes than non-military turbofan engines. In addition to the afterburn (A/B) power mode, there is an “intermediate” power mode of 100-108% of normal rated thrust (Spicer et al., 2009, 1992, 1989, 1987). The special feature of the A/B power mode is that raw fuel is added to an already hot exhaust to generate more thrust. Exhaust temperatures in the A/B mode gets too hot for traditional sampling probes and methods, thereby requiring modifications for successful measurements (Spicer et al., 2009, 1992, 1989, 1987). Though very high temperatures are reached in the A/B mode, combustion is very inefficient due to low oxygen content of the exhaust gas³.

Excluding afterburn power mode, military turbofan engine emission profiles are like other turbofan engines, especially for gaseous pollutants (Spicer et al., 2009, 1992, 1989, 1987). With increasing power, HC and CO emissions decrease. NO_x emissions increase with increasing power. Particle emission data are less conclusive due to limited measurements. Particle emissions measured as smoke numbers showed highest smoke numbers at 75% to intermediate power and lowest at idle to 30% of normal rated power (Spicer et al., 1989, 1987). With relatively old particle size distribution methods, Spicer et al. (1989) observed that particle sizes were larger than 24 nm, with a mode in their 42 nm bin. With an SMPS and other methods in validation, Rogers et al. (2005) observed highest particle number concentration (not EI) at idle and lowest at 70-80%. BC mass also decreased with increasing power for the F404-GE-400 engine studied (Rogers et al., 2005). Rogers et al. (2005) observed particle GMD at the different power modes to all be around 30 nm.

Due to very high temperatures at the A/B power measurements have been conducted at some distance from the engine exit plane (EEP). Test cell measurements used an “augmentor” tube, which dilutes the exhaust, and a partial afterburn test point, A/B zone 1 (Spicer et al., 1989, 1987); the sampling probe was located after the “augmentor” tube. On-wing sampling was conducted 38 m from EEP during A/B measurements (23 m for lower power modes) with a modified sampling probe (Spicer et al., 2009). Due to difficulty with A/B power mode, there are no measurements of particulate emissions at this power even from distance (Spicer et al., 2009, 1989, 1987). A/B CO and HC emissions were higher than all non-idle power settings. A/B NO_x emissions varied for the different engines tested at A/B power, but were generally low like the low power modes (Spicer et al., 2009, 1992, 1989, 1987).

2.3.2.2 Auxiliary power units (APUs)

APUs are small turbofan engines providing power for the different power needs of an aircraft especially during airport turnarounds. These power needs include electrical power and environmental control (air conditioning) when ground power and/or air is not available at the airport, and bleed air for main engine start (Fleuti and Hofmann, 2005). At airports where ground power is not available or is unreliable, the APU may run for a long period during aircraft

³ <https://www.airspacemag.com/flight-today/how-things-work-afterburners-18481403/?page=1>

turnaround (Padhra, 2018). For airport air quality, some airports with ground power units (GPUs) limit APU usage to 5 minutes after arrival and 5 minutes before departure (Fleuti and Hofmann, 2005; Padhra, 2018; Winther et al., 2015). At Copenhagen, APU usage exceeding the 5-minute limits (up to 45 mins depending on the size of the aircraft) may be permitted if temperatures fall below -10 °C or above 25 °C (Winther et al., 2015). While these limits exist, very few airlines comply; Padhra (2018) estimated a 6% compliance to this regulation (Padhra, 2018).

Padhra's analysis (2018) also estimated 16 min ± 10.5 min (standard deviation) median APU run time. In some instances, APU runtime were up to 45 min (Padhra, 2018). Though a small engine, the contribution to airport pollution may become significant with such long runtime. Some APU contributions to airport pollution have been calculated: Stettler et al. (2011) estimated 6% contribution to airport PM_{2.5} emissions; Winther et al. (2015) estimated 5% contribution to Copenhagen airport (CPH) particle number, 8% to particle mass, and 4% to NO_x emissions; Watterson et al. (2004) estimated 6% contribution to NO_x emissions at London Heathrow airport (LHR). Using remote sensing methods, Schäfer et al. (2001) observed a similar order of magnitude for CO and NO_x EIs from APUs and main engines at idle.

The power settings for APUs depends on the power service being provided. These power modes include (Fleuti and Hofmann, 2005; ICAO-9889, 2020; Lobo et al., 2015): "no load" (NL) or "idle", where no external power requirements are made on the APU; "400Hz" or "electrical generator"; "Environmental Control systems" (ECS) or "pre-conditioned air supply" (PCA), "bleed air" for main engine start (MES) or "Motor Engine". The MES is the highest power demand and NL, the lowest power demand. Engine fuel flow and exhaust gas temperature (EGT) increase with increasing power output. However, most available data do not distinguish between the different power settings.

Generally, APUs show similar CO and HC emission profiles to larger turbofan engines. CO and HC decrease with increasing power demand (Bulzan et al., 2010; Crayford and Johnson, 2011; Khandelwal et al., 2019; Kinsey et al., 2012). Observed NO_x emissions were different; while some studies observed no change in NO_x emissions but increase in NO to NO_x ratio (Khandelwal et al., 2019; Kinsey et al., 2012), others observed some increase in NO_x emission with increasing power (Bulzan et al., 2010; Crayford and Johnson, 2011).

Particle mass EIs decreased with increasing power demand for GTCP85 series (Bulzan et al., 2010; Kinsey et al., 2012; Lobo et al., 2015). A Rolls Royce Artouste Mk113 APU had higher PM mass concentration (mg/m³) at full power than at idle (Crayford and Johnson, 2011). Lobo et al. (2015) observed lowest PM number EIs at highest power. Kinsey et al.'s (2012) study was inconclusive in PM number EIs as different research groups in the same campaign showed different particle number EI profiles; some were u-shaped with maximum at highest power, others showed no variation with power. For the Kinsey et al.'s group (2012), using Fischer Tropsch fuel (alternative fuel) reduced PM number and mass EI, and had a clear profile of decreasing EIs with increasing exhaust gas temperature (EGT). Crayford et al. observed higher smoke number (SN) and PM number concentrations (1/cm³) at full power than at idle (Crayford and Johnson, 2011).

2.3.2.3 Turboshift engines

Turboshift engines are primarily used on helicopters to drive a transmission supplying the power needs of the helicopter. Engine emission performance tests have been conducted on turboshift engines in military applications as well as the effects of fuel composition on emission performance.

Variable observations were made for particulate emissions probably due to differences in sampling methods, dilution location and distance of the probe from EEP. Some studies were biased towards nvPM emissions from T63-A-700 (T63) engines (Cain et al., 2013; Corporan et al., 2007, 2004; Kinsey et al., 2019), and T700-GE-700 (T700) and T700-GE-701C (T701C) engines (Corporan et al., 2010), without modifications to the sampling system to specifically exclude volatile species. The bias is due to high dilution and high sampling temperature, which prevent or reduce the formation of volatile particles (Cain et al., 2013). Others targeted volatile particulate matter and speciation including organics and sulphur species also from T63 engines (Drozd et al., 2012; Kinsey et al., 2019), T700 and T701C engines (Cheng et al., 2009), and a C-T53-L13B engine (Chen et al., 2006).

There was a general agreement in particle number emissions. Particulate number emissions (concentrations and EIs) and geometric mean diameter (GMD) increased with increasing power (Cain et al., 2013; Corporan et al., 2010, 2004; Kinsey et al., 2019). For particle mass emissions, there was an increase in total (TC), elemental (EC) and organic carbon (OC) particle mass with increasing power for the T700 and T701C engines in EIs (Corporan et al., 2010) and mass concentrations (Cheng et al., 2009); however, the OC fraction decreased with increasing power. Smoke numbers from the T700 and T701C engines increased with increasing power (Corporan et al., 2010).

For the T63 engine, Corporan et al. (2004), whose study is biased towards nvPM, observed higher PM mass concentrations (mg/m^3) at cruise than at idle. Drozd et al. (2012) observed lower total particle mass EIs ($\text{mg}/\text{kg}_{\text{fuel}}$) at cruise than at idle. Drozd et al.'s speciation study (2012) revealed that there was a significant contribution of lubrication oil to the particulate organic aerosols. They also observed that sulphate aerosols were only a small fraction of the total particulate matter emissions. Kinsey et al. (2019), also with a T63 engine, observed higher total OC concentration (both gas and particulate) at idle than at cruise.

According to these studies on turboshift engines, the general emissions profiles for gaseous emissions of CO, HC and NO_x of turboshift engines were like those of turbofan engines. CO and HC emissions decrease with increasing power. NO_x emissions increase with increasing power. The studied engines are of different design ages. T701C is the newest turboshift design, and T700 is a newer design than the T63. The newer the engine design, the higher the combustion efficiency (Cheng et al., 2009; Corporan et al., 2010; Drozd et al., 2012). This implies lower emissions of HC and CO, but higher NO_x emissions from the newer engine design. PM number emissions were also lower from the newer engines.

With alternative fuels, there was significant decrease in certain emissions species (Cain et al., 2013; Cheng et al., 2009; Corporan et al., 2010, 2007, 2004; Drozd et al., 2012; Kinsey et al., 2019). All studies with PM measurements observed lower PM emissions with alternative fuels than with conventional fuels. Lower PM emissions were attributed to the absence or lower

concentrations of soot precursors like aromatics. In a plume measurement 4.14 m from EEP, nucleation mode was observed below 7 nm with JP-8 fuel (containing 0.14 wt % sulphur), which was absent with in the case of the paraffinic fuel; this was attributed to the absence of sulphur in the paraffinic fuel (Cheng et al., 2009).

2.3.2.4 Turboprop engines

Turboprop engines are like turboshaft engines; however, the turboprop engine is directly connected to and used to spin a propeller. Emission measurements were primarily conducted on turboprop engines for military purposes as in the T56 series III engines on C-130 Hercules (C-130H) aircraft (Chan et al., 2013; Cheng et al., 2008; Corporan et al., 2008; Spicer et al., 2009; Vaught et al., 1971) and T56-series II engines (Skidmore, 1986). Turboprop engines are also used in commercial aviation with very few emission performance data publicly available (Klapmeyer and Marr, 2012).

Power in turboprop engines is reported as shaft horsepower (shp). Turboprop engines are run at an optimum engine revolution per minute (RPM); this means that increasing power does not result in increase in engine RPM, but an increase in turbine inlet temperature (Vaught et al., 1971). Here, it is important to mention the untraditional power modes (Cheng et al., 2008; Corporan et al., 2008; Şöhret et al., 2015; Spicer et al., 2009; Vaught et al., 1971). For low power modes, there are the low-speed ground idle (LSGI, ~4% of take-off power) or holding, the high-speed ground idle (HSGI, ~7% of take-off power) or taxi, the flight idle (FI, ~20% of take-off) or near flight idle or approach. Higher power modes include climb, reverse, cruise (~41% of take-off power), normal power (~85% of take-off), maximum power or take-off (100%). The military engines have military power settings, normal military mode and military mode with air bleed (Chan et al., 2013).

The gaseous emission profiles observed for the T56 series engines are like those of turboshaft engines (Chan et al., 2013; Cheng et al., 2008; Corporan et al., 2008; Spicer et al., 2009; Vaught et al., 1971). CO emissions decreased unidirectionally with increasing power for most studies. The highest CO EIs were observed at LSGI with a sharp decrease at higher power settings. Chan et al. (2013) and Vaught et al. (1971) observed a slight increase in CO emission indices at take-off. Chan et al. (2013) also observed this increase in military mode with bleed air.

HC emissions were highest at low power modes and decreased with increasing power. Like CO, HC was highest at LSGI. In Chan et al.'s study (2013), where the lowest power mode was HSGI, highest HC emissions were observed at HSGI. Chan et al. (2013) observed a slight increase in the military mode with bleed air in HC emission.

NO_x EIs were lower at low power modes than at high power modes for all studies. Similar observations were made in the plume measurement by Klapmeyer and Marr (2012) of the Pratt and Whitney (PW) turboprop engine, PW123, on a De Havilland Canada Dash 8 (DHC8) aircraft. Klapmeyer and Marr (2012) observed higher NO_x EI at take-off than at idle. Chan et al. (2013) and Vaught et al. (1971) observed some plateauing in NO_x emission indices above 75% of maximum power, with a slight decrease in the military power modes (Chan et al., 2013).

Particle emissions were measured as smoke number (SN), particle number (PN), particle mass, and particle size distribution (PSD). SN increased with increasing power, with the highest observed at take-off and the lowest at LSGI (Corporan et al., 2008; Skidmore, 1986; Vaught et al., 1971). Smoke numbers for T56 series III (Vaught et al., 1971) were higher than those of the series II engines (Skidmore, 1986). More recent smoke number measurements by Corporan et al. (2008) for the T56-A-15 engine were comparable to the T56-A-7 engine (series II) reported by Skidmore (1986).

Particle number emission indices decreased with increasing power (Chan et al., 2013; Corporan et al., 2008). Chan et al. (2013) observed the lowest PN-EI at military power, which was about the same as at take-off. Due to the absence of loss corrections in Chan et al.'s study (2013), EIs from this study are about three times lower than those of Corporan et al. (2008). Klapmeyer et al.'s plume study (2012) on the DCH8 also observed lower average PM number EI at take-off than at idle. In addition, particle GMD increased with increasing power both at EEP (Chan et al., 2013; Cheng et al., 2008; Corporan et al., 2008) and at 15 m from EEP (Corporan et al., 2008).

Particle mass emissions were lower at high power modes. Corporan et al. (2008) observed an increase in particle mass emission from LSGI to a plateau at HSGI and FI after which mass decreased at higher power modes. Chan et al. (2013) had the same observation with maximum PM mass EI at HSGI (their lowest power mode) and decrease with increasing power, with lowest observation at military mode with bleed air.

Like the turboshaft engines, alternative fuel studies were conducted for the T56-A-15 turboprop engine using Camelina-Hydro-processed Esters and Fatty Acids, C-HEFA (Chan et al., 2013). Likewise, there was significant decrease in PM emissions with C-HEFA. PM GMD was also significantly smaller with C-HEFA than with the F-34 fuel used in this study (F-34 is a NATO version of JP-8, used by other studies on turboprop engines). There was slight but significant decrease in CO emissions, with highest reductions at HSGI than at other power modes. However, they observed higher, though insignificant, HC emissions with the C-HEFA fuel than with F-34 except at military mode with bleed air. There was no difference in NO_x emissions. The changes in emissions with power for the C-HEFA were the same as with the F-34 fuel.

2.3.2.5 Reciprocating or piston engines

Piston engines (also known as reciprocating engines) are a special class of engines with different modes of operation than other previously mentioned engine classes. Piston engines are generally run on rich fuel mix, that is, low air-fuel ratios (AFR) at almost all power modes; the leanest power mode is cruise (FOCA, 2007a, 2007b, 2007c; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). Piston engines are either air cooled or liquid cooled. As a result, at higher power modes, where engine temperatures are bound to increase, a rich fuel mix is used to provide additional cooling through evaporative cooling (FOCA, 2007c). In addition to cooling, piston engines may be run on full-rich fuel mix to make operation easier for inexperienced pilots; the pilots manually control fuel injection on majority of the aircrafts with piston engines (FOCA, 2007a; Yacovitch et al., 2016). General levels of fuel mix richness are idle > taxi ≈ take-off > cruise (FOCA, 2007a, 2007c; Yacovitch et al., 2016). Running on rich fuel mix implies that combustion in piston engines is relatively inefficient and incomplete.

Piston engines may be 4- to 6-cylinder horizontally opposed engines (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). There are also radial piston engines like the 9-cylinder radially opposed (star-like) engine (Czyż et al., 2018; Jerzy Merkisz et al., 2010). Like turboprop engines, power generated by piston engines spin a propeller which may be fixed- or variable-pitched (Scott Research laboratory, 1970). For piston engines, however, increase in power output results in increase in engine RPM (Czyż et al., 2018; FOCA, 2007a). Power output for piston engines is also reported as horsepower with special power mode definitions as brake horsepower, propeller horsepower (FOCA, 2007a; Rezy et al., 1979). Piston engines are also the only aviation engines using leaded fuel; there is however an unleaded fuel option that may be used on smaller engines (FOCA, 2007a).

Due to the rich fuel mix, the emission profile for piston engines is different than the above engine classes. With the overall rich fuel mix at all power modes, observed CO emissions are very high and do not vary much with power setting (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). Where there was more variation in AFR, CO was highest at take-off and climb (Czyż et al., 2018; FOCA, 2007a). With leaning during climb and/or cruise, CO decreased significantly (FOCA, 2007a; Jerzy Merkisz et al., 2014; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). Similarly, engines run on full rich mix at all power modes had little variation in HC emissions with power setting (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). HC emissions were however slightly higher at critical power settings such as approach and take-off (FOCA, 2007a).

On engines with automatic lean control, HC emissions were highest at take-off (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). Leaning at cruise only moderately reduced HC emissions (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970). NO_x emissions were highest at cruise when run as lean cruise (FOCA, 2007a). Otherwise, NO_x concentrations were very low or below detection limit (FOCA, 2007a; Scott Research laboratory, 1970).

So far, nvPM emission data available were from measurements conducted by FOCA (2007b) on Lyc O-320 and Lyc O-360 series engines. Due to lead present in primary piston engine fuel, AVGAS 100LL, lead bromide (PbBr₂) was observable in the measured particle emissions. The unleaded fuel alternative for smaller engines is AVGAS 91/96UL. In both fuel cases, FOCA (2007b) observed increase in total particle number concentration and total mass concentration with increasing power, with maximum at take-off on the Lyc O-360 engine series. For the Lyc O-320 series, number emission did not show a significant trend with power setting but had maximum mass emission at approach. The Lyc O-320 ran less rich than Lyc O-360 resulting in different PM emission profiles. The use of unleaded fuel significantly decreased nvPM emission. Unleaded fuel alternatives in fuel dependence test resulted in the smaller particle GMD.

2.3.3 Outlook

One recurring theme for the non-regulated engines is the lack of publicly available data. Where data were available, there was no clear and consistent standardized measurement method or power setting across the different studies. Engine properties for which emissions were measured in some cases are unknown, for instance, APUs. A standardized test program with loss corrections would improve the quality and usability of available data for air quality modelling and development of inventories.

In addition to missing engine characteristics, particulate emission data are limited for most engine classes. For military turbofan, turboprop and turboshaft engines, these data are primarily from the 1970s and 1980s; methods applied are relatively old. For instance, Spicer's group concluded in the 1980s that tested engines were clean based on smoke measurements and existing particulate measurement methods. Those filtration methods miss the ultrafine particles that are now known to have severe health impacts. Also, there are scarcely any data, gaseous and particulate, available for the civilian counterpart to aircrafts engines in military application.

2.4 Volatile particulate matter

Ultrafine particles are released during combustion processes on the one hand as solid particles, mainly in the form of soot particles. The diameter of the particles when released is typically between 10 nm and a few tens of nm. These particles are referred to as non-volatile particulate matter (nvPM). After release, the number of these particles remains relatively constant; their diameter and mass may increase due to condensation of gases and other deposits on their surface.

On the other hand, after the cooling of hot combustion exhaust gases, liquid droplets and nucleation nuclei of nitrates and sulphates are formed, on the surfaces of which further substances can condense. Typical diameters of these particles are a few nanometres shortly after formation. Both the number and mass change significantly during transport due to processes such as agglomeration, condensation, and evaporation on a time scale from one second to several tens of minutes. An effective emission rate can be derived from the number of particles in the cooled exhaust gas. These particles are referred to as volatile or semi-volatile ultrafine particles. In the following, the simplified term volatile particulate matter (vPM) is used.

Timko et al. (2013) report on measurements during the AAFEX campaign. Particles were measured at distances of 30 m and 300 m behind an engine at different power settings and for different types of fuel used. At distances with moderate dilution, about 10 to 50 times more particles (sum of vPM and nvPM) were observed as compared closer to the engine exit at 30 m. There were more particles for lower power settings. The ratio of organic to sulphur mass was about 10. At high power, fuel with low sulphur and zero aromatics increased the number of nucleation mode particles.

Wong et al. (2014) report on a detailed microphysical modelling of the formation of organic and sulfuric coatings on soot particles in the near field (distances less than 1000 m) behind an engine at 7% maximum thrust. Soot-soot coagulation was found to be significant. Soot coating was mainly by organics with low vapour pressure (characteristic substances $C_{20}H_{12}$, $C_{22}H_{12}$). There was major soot coating after some cooling of the exhaust gas and before dilution becomes dominant. High ambient temperatures tended to suppress soot microphysics.

Wong et al. (2015) investigated, using microphysical modelling, the role of organic emissions in the formation of vPM in the near field (distances less than 1000 m) behind an aircraft engine at 7% maximum thrust. The nucleation cores were mostly created by sulfuric acid and water, on which then organic material condensed. The presence of organic vapours did not promote

nucleation of new particles. The following refers to a distance of 1000 m. For temperatures above about 12 °C or low relative humidity, sulfuric acid and water condensed on the soot particles and the number of nucleation mode particles dropped and their mass was dominated by organics. For temperatures below 8°C or high relative humidity, the mass of nucleation mode particles was dominated by sulfuric acid and water. Almost all sulfuric acid mass condensed on the soot particles (high temperatures) or was part of the nucleation particles (low temperatures). For the organic mass, at most 4% was condensed on the particles, with a negligible amount at temperatures above about 20°C.

Peck et al. (2016) modelled the evolution of surrogate organic emissions in an aircraft exhaust plume for low and high power settings of the engine. They found that the nucleation mode particles have a sulphate core, but their mass is mostly organic material. At low engine power, there was only slow condensation of organics (limiting factor) on a few soot particles. At high power, there were more soot particles and hence more organic material condensed.

Yu et al. (2019) studied the mode-specific, semi-volatile chemical composition of particulate matter based on the AAFEX data at a distance of 30 m behind an engine at different power settings. At low power, the mass of vPM was mainly organic material, while at high power it was roughly half organic and half other material. At 4% maximum power, the organic mass of nucleation mode particles consisted mainly of aromatics while at 85%, lubrication oil dominated.

2.5 Emission inventories

An emission inventory typically comprises a dataset with amounts of emission, in terms of mass, for the most relevant air pollutants and greenhouse gas species. Emissions are split by source type, time, and location. Different levels of spatial and temporal resolution are possible, depending on the scope and purpose of the inventory.

With regard to aircraft emissions, emission inventories usually report only emissions related to the landing and take-off (LTO) cycle. This LTO cycle covers activities up to 3000 feet (914 metres) above ground level, which is roughly equivalent to the altitude of the atmospheric boundary layer at daytime. Emissions below this altitude are expected to have the dominant influence on local ground-level air quality parameters. This 3000-foot boundary is also used as the cut-off for reporting emissions for air pollution under EMEP (Gothenburg Protocol) and the EU National Emission Ceilings Directive (2016/2284/EU), which implies that emissions at higher altitudes are not included in the emission reduction targets for air pollutants. As a result, national emission inventories often pay limited attention to what happens at higher altitudes.

2.5.1 Airport level (single airport)

At airport level, the compilation of an emission inventory is typically motivated by the permitting process, which requires an Environmental Impact Report investigating continued or planned activities at the airport in question. Other potential reasons for compiling an emission inventory are to perform benchmarking or to monitor emission trends in light of emission mitigation plans or actions.

Since individual airports are not subject to international regulations covering the regular reporting of emissions by country, these emission inventories do not have a fixed format, scope, or methodology. The scope of the inventory will likely be influenced by the issues that are thought to be most important locally. Given the narrower focus when considering only a single airport, it is usually possible to include more detailed information in the analysis and perform a more comprehensive modelling of the emissions. The emission inventory will typically include all significant emission sources at the airport and cover a full calendar year and a range of pollutant species, such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur oxides (SO_x), particulate matter (PM), and hydrocarbons (HC) / non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOCs).

The overall emissions calculated for an airport depend on:

- The considered emission sources (e.g., aircraft only or also emissions from GSE, motor traffic, and other sources),
- the applied conventions (e.g., the height up to which aircraft movements are considered or the extent to which landside motor traffic is considered),
- the applied methodologies (e.g., using emission rates and times-in-mode of the certification LTO or using performance-based values),
- and the applied level of detail (e.g., approaches to estimate GSE emissions or information on the actual aircraft/engine combinations).

Duchene et al. (2004) investigated the influence of different emission models on the inventory of an airport, and Fleuti and Maraini (2012) carried out a sensitivity study of how assumptions and applied levels of detail on aircraft traffic affects the overall emission.

The ICAO Airport Air Quality Manual (ICAO-9889, 2020), provides guidance for the calculation of aircraft-related emissions at an airport for different levels of complexity.

2.5.2 Regional level (Country, District)

2.5.2.1 General

EU countries are subject to emission legislation (NECD: 2016/2284; CLRTAP: 2019/1021)(EC, 2019, 2016), requiring the annual reporting of air pollutant emissions by sector, including the aviation sector. Currently, these national inventories require the reporting of particle emissions only in terms of mass (as PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, specifically), not in terms of particle numbers and/or particle size distributions.

The country-level emission inventory distinguishes between the different airports in the countries. Therefore, it is constructed as such and not by combining separate airport level inventories. This is motivated by the requirement that a consistent and transparent methodology is used for all years and sources.

The full requirements on data and methodologies used are specified in the CLRTAP guidelines (ECE, 2014) and the EMEP/EEA inventory guidebook (EMEP/EEA, 2019), which covers 5 specific emission sources (and associated reporting categories) related to aviation:

- Domestic airport traffic (LTO)
- International airport traffic (LTO)
- Domestic cruise traffic
- International cruise traffic
- Military aviation

The LTO emissions and military aviation are compulsory categories, the climb, cruise, and descent (CCD) emissions are so-called 'memo-items', which do not count toward the country total but are included for completeness. These 'memo-items' are not mandatory for reporting. Note that emissions from stationary combustion units, ground transport and other mobile combustion units (e.g., GPU) are not reported under the aviation category in the inventory but are included within mobile machinery.

2.5.2.1.1 LTO emissions

In modelling the LTO emissions, countries can opt for 3 methodological Tiers of increasing complexity and expected accuracy. In short:

- For Tier 1, activity data exists of either fuel sales or total number of LTO flights divided into domestic and international usage. The EMEP/EEA Guidebook then offers default emission factors (either per kg fuel or per LTO, both assuming a typical fleet composition).
- For Tier 2, information on the number of LTO flights by aircraft type is used in combination with aircraft-specific LTO emission factors.
- For Tier 3, information on the aircraft type and destination of each flight is used in combination with more detailed aircraft/engine- and LTO phase-specific emission factors.

Especially for Visual Flight Rules and helicopter flights, it is expected that data limitations will lead to the use of a Tier 1 methodology for these flights. Furthermore, given the large variation in PM emission intensity between different aircraft types, the Guidebook advises the use of at least a Tier 2 methodology to calculate PM emissions (EMEP/EEA, 2019). In case aircraft emissions are considered a key category (which refers to the most important sources in the national total emissions, adding up to 80% of the cumulative emissions), the use of a Tier 2 or Tier 3 methodology is mandatory.

The Guidebook notes the availability of emission factors for CO, NO_x, HC from the ICAO engine emission databank (EEDB, 2021) and lists the First Order Approximation v.3 (FOA3) method for deriving PM emission factors from the EEDB reported smoke number. Note that from EEDB version 28 onwards, the EEDB also contains non-volatile PM emission factors for all certified in-production engines.

For the duration of the different LTO phases (time-in-mode), the Guidebook advises the use of the ICAO default values when no specific data is available (listed in Table 2-1 below).

Operating mode	Thrust setting	Time in operating mode (minutes)
Take-off	100%	0.7
Climb-out	85%	2.2
Approach/landing	30%	4.0
Taxi/ground idle	7%	26.0

Table 2-1 Default LTO cycle (EMEP/EEA, 2019)

In addition to emission data tables, EU countries are also required, under CLRTAP and NECD, to submit a gridded emission inventory, which is required for reporting every 4 years. This inventory contains a separate data layer with spatially allocated aviation LTO emissions. The gridded data are required at a horizontal resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (equivalent to about 5 to 10 km horizontal resolution depending on the location in Europe). This implies that for most airports all emissions will be located within the same grid cell. However, for take-off and approach emissions will likely be partly located in adjacent grid cells.

2.5.2.1.2 Cruise emissions

Calculating the emissions from climb, cruise, and descent activities is not mandatory and the methods described in the EMEP/EEA Guidebook are less detailed than for the LTO emissions.

At Tier 1 level, the fuel use for CCD activities is estimated by subtracting the fuel use for LTO from the national total fuel sales for aviation. The Guidebook offers an emission calculation tool from which emission factors for the main air pollutants including volatile and non-volatile PM can be derived per amount of fuel for CCD activities.

At Tier 2 or 3 level, the same emission tool can be used to estimate cruise emissions based on the aircraft type and flight distance, which would require more information on the annual number of flights, aircraft types and related flight distances (e.g., based on departure and destination airport).

2.5.2.2 Methods to derive a PM emission factor from the EEDB reported smoke number

Up until version 27 (August 2020) of the ICAO EEDB, the databank only contained the smoke number for the 4 LTO phases and not a final (nv)PM mass or number-based emission factor. There are several methods/relationships available to derive a non-volatile PM emission factor from the smoke number. Several older methodologies are reported by Kugele et al. (2005). The most relevant current methodologies are discussed below.

2.5.2.2.1 First Order Approximation 3 (FOA3)

The method mentioned by the 2019 EMEP/EEA Guidebook is the First Order Approximation method version 3 (FOA3), which is explained in detail by Wayson et al. (2009). In addition to deriving a non-volatile PM (mass-based) emission factor from the reported smoke number, the FOA3 method also allows the approximation of a volatile PM emission factor, which

consists of two components; one is based on the fuel sulphur content, while the volatile organics can be estimated by taking into account the engine HC emission factor.

2.5.2.2.2 First Order Approximation 4 (FOA4)

In the most recent ICAO Doc 9889 Airport Air Quality Manual (v.2) a new methodology, the First Order Approximation method v.4 (FOA4), is presented. FOA4 estimates non-volatile PM emissions from the reported engine smoke number, as well as the non-volatile particle numbers and particle size distribution. The methodology is based on the work done in CAEP/11 and previously published by Agarwal et al. (2019). The FOA4 methodology follows several steps.

$EI_{m,e}(BC)$, the emission index of BC mass at the engine exit plane (mg/kg fuel) is calculated as follows:

1. $C_{BC,i}$, the BC concentration (mg/m³) at the instrument sampling point is estimated using an experimentally derived correlation between smoke numbers and measured BC concentrations.
2. $EI_{m,i}(BC)$, the BC emission index (mg/kg fuel) at the instrument sampling point is calculated by multiplying $C_{BC,i}$ with the volumetric flow rate Q (m³/ kg fuel).
3. A system loss correction factor (k_{slm}) is calculated, representing the loss between the engine exit plane and the instrument sampling point.
4. $EI_{m,e}(BC)$ is calculated by multiplying $EI_{m,i}(BC)$ with the loss correction factor k_{slm} .

The FOA4 method assumes default values for the geometric mean diameter (GMD, in nanometre) of the particle size distributions, dependent on the flight mode (see Table 2-2).

Flight mode	GMD (nm)
Take-off	40
Climb out	40
Approach	20
Idle	20

Table 2-2 Default GMD for use in FOA4 method.

In the FOA4 method, the particle number emission index at the engine exit plane ($EI_{N,e}(BC)$) can then be estimated using Equation 1 below, which relates the BC mass to the GMD and an effective soot density of 1 g/cm³ (ρ), assuming a log-normal distribution with a geometric standard deviation (σ) of 1.8.

Equation 1 (ref.: ICAO-9889, 2020)

$$EI_{NvPMnumber,e,k} \left(\frac{\#}{kg \text{ fuel}} \right) = \frac{6 \cdot EI_{NvPMmass,e,k} \left(\frac{g}{kg \text{ fuel}} \right) \cdot N_r}{\pi \cdot \rho \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \right) \cdot GMD_k^3 (nm^3) \cdot e^{4.5(\ln(\sigma))^2}}$$

Agarwal et al. (2019) present a method to derive the GMD by flight mode from the BC concentration using an experimentally derived correlation:

- $C_{BC,e}$, the BC concentration (mg/m^3) at the engine exit plane is calculated by dividing $El_{m,e}(BC)$ with the volumetric flow rate Q .
- $C_{BC,c}$, the BC concentration at the combustor exit is then estimated using the ratio between the ambient air pressure (p_a) and the pressure at the combustor exit (p_{t4}).
- The GMD is then estimated using an experimentally derived correlation between $C_{BC,c}$ and the GMD.

The particle number emission index is then derived in the same way as described for the FOA4 method, only the calculated GMD is used instead of the default value.

2.5.2.2.3 Fractal aggregates model

Teoh et al. (2019), expand on the simple theoretical derivation between particle mass (M) and number (N_s) presented in Equation 1, which characterizes the particles as spheres with density ρ and a lognormal distribution of diameters with geometric mean diameter (number median diameter) (GMD) and geometric standard deviation σ (GSD).

Teoh et al. (2019) present a more detailed description of particle morphology and its effect on e.g. the effective soot density. Equation 1 is extended to include several empirically calibrated coefficients that account for particle morphology. Two sets of parameter values for the Transmission Electron Microscopy prefactor (kTEM) and the Transmission Electron Microscopy exponent (DTEM) are presented in their publication (see Table 2-3).

	kTEM	DTEM
Parameter set 1	$1.621 * 10^{-5}$	0.39
Parameter set 2	0.0125	0.8

Table 2-3 Parameter sets.

Compared to the methodology described by Agarwal et al. (2019) (parameterized with an effective soot density of $1\text{g}/\text{cm}^3$ and a GSD of 1.8), the Fractal Aggregates (FA) model predicts more particles with diameters larger than about 20 nm, and fewer particles with diameters smaller than about 20 nm compared (see Figure 2-7).

Figure 2-7: Ratio of predicted particle numbers Fractal Aggregate Model (N_{FA}) versus Agarwal et al. (N_s) for $\rho_0 = 1.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\rho = 1.0 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and different values of the GSD. Red: 1.4. Green: 1.6. Blue: 1.8.

2.5.2.3 Netherlands aviation emission inventory

For the Dutch emission inventory, TNO has developed the CLEO model to annually determine aviation emissions (Dellaert and Hulskotte, 2017). The model includes emissions from aircraft engines (LTO only), APUs, tyre and brake wear, ground support equipment (GSE), and aircraft fuelling and fuel handling. With regard to aircraft emissions, the model uses the number of LTO flights by aircraft type and airport to calculate LTO emissions, using mostly emission factors from the ICAO EEDB. For the larger airports, airport specific taxi-times are used for most years. APU types by aircraft and APU fuel and emission factors were based mostly on Watterson et al. (2004).

PM emission factors have been derived from the smoke number as reported in the EEDB. Previously, the 'DLR correlation method' as explained in Kugele et al. (2005) was used to derive the BC emission intensity from the smoke number, while the volatile part was estimated using a simple fraction of 60% vPM within total PM. However, after recent model updates, the BC emission intensity is now determined using the FOA4 methodology extended with the calculation of GMD s and the Fractal aggregates model, as detailed in Section 2.5.2.2. Furthermore, the emission intensity of volatile PM is determined using the FOA4 methodology. For non-regulated engines (e.g. piston or turboshaft engines), emission factors were collected from a variety of sources, such as AP-42 and FOCA (Rindlisbacher, 2007; Rindlisbacher and Chabbey, 2015; US EPA, 1978). Partly because there is no obligation to report them, particle numbers have not been calculated in the past for the Dutch emission inventory.

2.5.3 Global level

At European level, gridded inventories of aviation emissions can be compiled by combining the gridded emission inventories at country-level or by combining country-level emission inventories and performing a separate gridding process. Given that national emission inventories are not available everywhere around the globe, even in Europe, and that national emission inventories may have issues (e.g., regarding completeness or consistency) that make

it unfit for modelling air quality, the latter method has been used for many years to provide emission input to dispersion models at continental to global level.

At European level, the TNO_MACC and CAMS-REG emission inventories (Kuenen et al., 2021, 2014) have been created by taking country-reported data, where possible, and complementing these with the best estimates for other countries. This created a complete database for Europe, which applies a consistent methodology for spatial distribution of emissions across the entire domain at a resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ ($\sim 6 \times 6$ km). This makes the database fit-for-purpose for air quality modelling at European scale. In a currently ongoing H2020 project (VERIFY), the same is being done for greenhouse gases and for a smaller domain in central Europe at a high resolution of about 1×1 km. These emission inventories are currently widely used for air quality modelling in Europe.

For aviation, these inventories represent the airports only as point sources, that is, all emissions from the aircraft are in a single location or grid cell. While for smaller airports this may lead to minimal anomalies, for larger airports as well as for the climb-out and approach emissions this will not be accurate. So far, this has received little attention, since the inventories focus on PM (mass only) and other pollutants such as NO_x for which aviation is only a relatively small source when considering all anthropogenic emissions.

For global modelling of air quality, the Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR), developed by JRC, contains global emissions for all anthropogenic sources of emissions at a resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ (about 10×10 km, dependent on the location). In contrast to the European emission inventories described above, this database is completely bottom-up, which implies that for all countries the emissions have been calculated by using activity data and emission factors, disregarding any available country level inventories. For particles, emissions of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and BC are reported in these emission grids. For aircraft, the emissions are provided for 4 different subcategories:

- Aviation landing and take-off (altitude 0-1 km)
- Aviation climbing and descent (1-9 km)
- Aviation cruise (9-13 km)
- Aviation supersonic (>13 km, minor source)

The information in this EDGAR database is based on the Aero2k project, which developed a global inventory of emissions and fuel use from aviation for 2002 and for 2025.

3 Dispersion modelling

Dispersion models provide a 3-dimensional concentration distribution of pollutants for subsequent time intervals. They are an important tool to supplement measurements that take place only at a few, specific locations. Dispersion modelling is also used to investigate future scenarios or to study specific processes of atmospheric dispersion. The range of dispersion models extends from simple analytic solutions based on physical conservation laws to complex numerical algorithms.

Generally, a dispersion model consists of a chain of models, for example:

1. Source model (e.g., localization of complex source systems)
2. Emission model (e.g., quantity, temporal behaviour)
3. Exhaust dynamics model (e.g., plume rise)
4. Meteorology model (e.g., boundary layer, wind field)
5. Transformation model (e.g., chemical conversions)
6. Deposition model (e.g., sedimentation, dry and wet deposition)
7. Core dispersion model (e.g., Gaussian, Eulerian, Lagrangian)
8. Result evaluation model (e.g., isolines, percentiles, background combination)

Some parts of this model chain may be easily replaceable (e.g., deposition velocities), some others not.

The setup of a dispersion model, the applied assumptions, and the applied input parameters depend on the context in which the dispersion calculation takes place, for example:

1. Standard application in agreement with national or international constraints
2. Screening run with simplified assumptions
3. Scientific research with elaborated input and modelling details
4. Conservative approach with a deliberate overestimation of concentration
5. Calculation with public data only for transparency constraints

In the context of aircraft and airports, all these scenarios and constraints have their practical applications.

3.1 Airport level

ICAO provides with the *Airport Air Quality Manual* (ICAO-9889, 2020) an extensive description of emission and dispersion calculation methodologies at airports, in particular, for aircraft main engines and APU. It includes a calculation methodology for nvPM mass and number emission indices (FOA4) based on work in the CAEP/11 cycle. Document 9889 is continuously improved in the current CAEP/12 cycle and a next update is expected towards the year 2022.

The CAEP of ICAO has evaluated several dispersion models, which are designed for local air quality (LAQ) studies at and around airports, in view of their applicability in CAEP work (ICAO, 2010, 2016). Some of these models are routinely applied in scientific projects and airport assessment procedures.

In the Project for the Sustainable Development of Heathrow (PSDH), several dispersion models were evaluated and compared against measurements (DfT, 2006). A summary of aspects relevant for airport dispersion modelling is provided by Arunachalam et al. with focus on Los Angeles Airport (Arunachalam et al., 2017). An extended guidance for a model-based quantification of the contribution of airport emissions to local air quality is given in the ACRP Report 71 (Kim et al., 2012).

A variety of modelling studies have been carried out at Zurich Airport. Some of these include comparisons of model-based emission inventories (Duchene et al., 2004), comparisons of modelled and measured concentrations (Fuller and Celikel, 2005; Ruf, 2013), and sensitivity studies (Fleuti and Maraini, 2012; Maraini, 2012).

Barrett et al. (2013) investigated the impact of aircraft plume dynamics on the predicted local air quality. It was observed that measured, aircraft-induced concentrations in the vicinity of airports do not reveal the usual inverse dependence on wind speed is related to the effects of plume dynamics. A simplified methodology to account for plume dynamics in the context of emission grids for airport dispersion modelling has been developed in a study by EUROCONTROL (Janicke, 2005).

3.2 Regional/Global level

Aviation is a source of anthropogenic emissions that perturb the chemical composition of the atmosphere. Up to now, only few studies have accessed the effect of aviation cruise emission on surface air quality. Generally, the impact of aircraft emissions on air quality are related to LTO emissions as they are emitted near ground level. It is also thought that, logically, they would impact the ground level PM concentration more than the non-LTO emissions. However, nearly 75% of the emissions are released above 7 km (Wilkerson et al., 2010), justifying the need for specific studies evaluating the impact of cruise emissions on surface air quality. Hence, different papers using different methodologies have been analysed and the main outcomes are summarised here after.

3.2.1 Dynamical approach

Cruise level is located usually between 9 and 11 km (e.g. 250 hPa), therefore aviation emissions can reach ground level mainly through dynamically induced vertical mixing. Whitt et al. (2011) made a comprehensive numerical experiment of commercial aviation emission transport from cruise to the surface. By only including vertical mixing via cloud processes and thereby neglecting the chemistry and scavenging processes, they identified that the tropospheric lifetime of the components of aviation emissions are shorter than average tropospheric mixing time calculated from their study. They give the example of tropospheric ozone for which the average chemical lifetime is evaluated to be 22 days; this is, on average, four times shorter than the timescale of a full mixing of the tropospheric column. Logically, they conclude that the cruise emission outside the tropics should not affect the ground level air quality compared to LTO and local airport emissions.

Hence, Whitt et al.'s (2011) conclusion would also apply to PM as their lifetime in the troposphere is estimated, on average, to be 10 days. The study also emphasises that the increase in spatial resolution in the future studies will not affect the main outcome of their study. Another important point made by the paper is that half of the commercial aviation emissions occur in rather thermo-dynamically stable regions (cruise level around 250 hPa), with one quarter of the mass of emissions occurring in the stratosphere, which is a very stable layer of the atmosphere (Figure 3-1). Hence, the study shows that the released cruise aviation emissions do not undergo the strong vertical mixing of the troposphere. Therefore, it is unlikely that they significantly affect the ground level air quality. However, the authors recommend that intense and localised emission events at cruise level (e.g., main aviation

corridors) should be studied using global or mesoscale models as they could locally affect the ground air quality on a short time scale at specific locations.

Fuel Burned (Tg)	Percent	Category
45.6	24	Stratosphere
143	76	Troposphere
13.3	7	315 K > theta > 300 K
46.3	25	330 K > theta > 315 K
49.7	26	345 K > theta > 330 K
28.2	15	360 K > theta > 345 K
7.45	5.2	Theta > 360 K
61.5	33	In ExTL
4.62	2.5	Above ExTL
46.5	25	
51.9	28	
46.7	25	
188	100	2006 Total

Figure 3-1 Commercial aviation fuel burned in the year 2006 disaggregated by background atmospheric properties (from Whitt et al., 2011).

Main outcomes:

- It is unlikely that cruise aviation emissions significantly affect ground level air quality.
- Intense and localised emission from cruise level events should be studied using global or mesoscale models as they could locally affect the ground air quality.

3.2.2 Physico-chemical approach

Lee et al. (2013) show that aviation emissions lead, globally, to less than 1% aerosol enhancement in the boundary layer and that the increase is mainly due to ammonium nitrate increase during cold seasons. The increase in the summer is statistically insignificant. They also show that aviation induced aerosol increase near the ground is highly dependent on background ammonia concentration and are, on a global level, primarily due to cruise level emissions rather than the landing and take-off emissions. Indeed, the authors show that the vertical aviation emissions repartitioning is species dependent (Figure 3-2). NO_x and SO₂ emissions are mainly released at cruise altitude while species such as CO and BC are emitted during LTO and the climb/descent cycle. They also show that the perturbation of PM_{2.5} in July is less than 0.2 % of the background PM_{2.5}. In January, PM_{2.5} increases by about 0.1 µg/m³ over the Midwest and East Coast of the US, in Europe and in East Asia. The increase is smaller (Barrett et al., 2010) but the spatial distribution of the perturbation is similar.

The larger NO_x emissions used by (Barrett et al., 2010) could be the explanation for the differences between the two studies. During wintertime, nitric acid (HNO₃) determines the effects of the non-LTO emissions on the boundary layer PM_{2.5} while sulphate (SO₄) is almost zero near the ground. In contrast, during the summer the sulphate aerosols dominate the PM_{2.5} perturbation. However, according to the authors, the resulting PM_{2.5} perturbation, including ammonium nitrate (NH₄NO₃) and SO₄, is not statistically significant at ground level according to the student t-test. The authors also discuss the significance of such small

perturbation in relation to the uncertainty of PM2.5 predictions in state-of-the-art models (e.g., 5 µg/m³ for CMAQ). They finally conclude that the overall impact of aviation emission on surface PM2.5 is minuscule, and that mortality cannot be determined from such a small signal with any certainty. The authors also performed sensitivity analysis regarding the ammonia (NH₃) emissions, which is a precursor of ammonium sulphate ((NH₄)₂SO₄) and NH₄NO₃ aerosols. They show that an increase in NH₃ emissions lead to an increase of the PM2.5 perturbation by more than 100 % (e.g., East coast of the US) relative to the perturbation with reference background NH₃.

The sensitivity study suggests that large uncertainties in background NH₃ must be considered when evaluating the aviation effects on surface aerosols concentration. Similarly to (Barrett et al., 2010), the cruise emission-induced secondary aerosol perturbations were statistically significant at some modelled grid points in the US, Europe and East Asia, and in the winter, NH₄NO₃ is the dominant species of the PM2.5 perturbation. However, the cruise aviation emission-induced perturbation is too small to be meaningful relative to uncertainty in state-of-the-art models.

units: [Tg yr ⁻¹]	NO _x (as NO)	CO	SO ₂	black carbon	organic carbon
LTO emissions	0.126 (9.5%)	0.624 (37.3%)	0.0167 (10.3%)	0.00134 (19.9%)	0.000446
climb/descent emissions	0.489 (36.9%)	0.732 (43.8%)	0.0518 (32.0%)	0.00296 (44.1%)	0.000985
cruise altitude emissions	0.712 (53.7%)	0.315 (18.8%)	0.0931 (57.6%)	0.00242 (36%)	0.000805
total emissions	1.347	1.692	0.164	0.007	0.002

Figure 3-2 Total annual emissions from aircraft used reported by Lee et al. (201) for year 1999.

Vennam et al. (2017) apply the Community Multi-scale Air Quality Mode (CMAQ) model to an overall Northern Hemispheric domain. They show that full-flight aviation emissions using the AEDT emission inventory contribute to 0.2% (0.013 µg/m³) of surface PM2.5, with rather strong discrepancies within the domain. These results are consistent with Yim et al. (2015) and Lee et al. (2013). Spatially, the perturbations occur near major urban corridors such as Eastern United States, Western Europe, and China. EU shows the highest annual mean relative impact (0.5% (0.031 µg/m³) compared to North America (0.4% (0.021 µg/m³)) and East Asia (0.2% (0.021 µg/m³)). These mean values are about twice higher than the global hemispheric mean (0.013 µg/m³). Note that the perturbation is slightly higher during winter months compared to the rest of the year.

The maximum PM2.5 aircraft-attributable contribution (AAC) is modelled over Europe (0.15 µg/m³) and is about 1.5 times higher than over North America and China. As previously shown in Lee et al. (2013), inorganic aerosols (ammonium sulphate and ammonium nitrate) contribute strongly to the total PM2.5. The sulphate aerosol has the larger contribution to PM2.5 total mass during summer and fall months (April-November), while during winter, due to the higher HNO₃ concentration (less HNO₃ reduction through photolysis) that can react with NH₃, more NO₃ aerosols are modelled during this period.

Moreover, Vennam et al. (2017) show that the transport of cruise emissions is highly influenced by the seasonal circulation pattern. The PM2.5 mass flux vertical profiles are highly

seasonal, underlining the influence of seasonal factors such precipitation patterns, wet deposition, chemical transformations, and cloud properties on PM intercontinental and vertical transport. The autumn season shows the highest PM_{2.5} AAC in the mid-troposphere region due to higher nitrate aerosol and nitric acid concentrations. The downward fluxes mainly explain, according to the authors, the transport of cruise emissions in the overall Northern Hemisphere during the winter when downdraft/westerlies are high and boundary layer/surface mixing is low. Finally, Vennam et al. (2017) show that compared to a fine grid resolution, a coarse grid produces up to 13 times higher PM_{2.5} aviation perturbation in North America. They explain that this important difference is mainly due to the inability of the coarse resolution simulation to capture nonlinearities in chemical processes especially near airport locations and other high emitter locations (e.g. urban areas).

Phoenix et al. (2019) use an updated version of the Community Atmosphere Model with Chemistry (CAM5) to perform present day and future simulations. The 2050 emission scenarios are produced based on projected population growth by 2050 but consider identical flight tracks and flight distance. The scenarios assume future fuel efficiency or fuel type. In the case of the biofuel scenario, the soot emissions are divided by two and no sulphur is considered in the fuel as is usually done in other numerical study.

Globally, the aviation-induced increase in PM_{2.5} is mainly driven by the increase in sulphate (SO₄²⁻) and ammonium nitrate (NH₄NO₃) according to the simulations, with SO₄²⁻ perturbation much larger in proportion than NH₄NO₃ for both months. Moreover, the peak in OC and BC perturbations are small, consistent with Lee et al. (2013). The regional perturbations are also in agreement with Lee et al. (2013). The result show that the maximum present-day perturbation is located over China in January (1.4 µg/m³). The 2050 simulations show that the highest perturbation is reached in January, with a maximum increase of 3.5 µg/m³ for the fossil fuel scenario in Africa and 2.2 µg/m³ for the biofuel scenario in China.

The fact that the modal aerosol module does not assume that ammonia is in equilibrium between the gas and aerosol phase could explain the lower NH₄NO₃ perturbation in January compared to previous studies (Barrett et al., 2010). However, Phoenix et al. (2019) underline that due to the uncertainty in ammonia (NH₃) emissions and its crucial role in the NH₄NO₃ formation, the ground level aerosol perturbation due to cruise emission remains highly uncertain. The alternative scenario that contains less soot and no sulphur tend to enhance ozone formation and reduce the removal of NO₃ and N₂O₅ due to heterogeneous chemistry. Finally, the study show that aviation has a minor effect on increasing the frequency of extreme air quality events, and PM_{2.5} impact is very low (0.1%) compared to the reference simulation with no aviation emission.

Main outcomes of the presented papers:

- Full-flight aviation emissions, using the AEDT emission inventory, contribute up to 0.2% (0.013 µg/m³) to surface PM_{2.5}.
- Inorganic aerosols (ammonium sulphate and ammonium nitrate) contribute strongly to the total PM_{2.5}.
- The autumn season shows the highest PM_{2.5} AAC in the mid-tropospheric region due to higher nitrate aerosol and nitric acid concentrations.

- Nonlinearities in chemical processes especially near airport locations and other high emitter locations should be considered in future simulation as they could play a crucial role in increasing PM_{2.5} aviation perturbation.
- Hence, the authors recommend considering, in more detail, the role of NH₃ in NH₄NO₃ formation using more detailed global observations of NH₃ emissions, as its emission rate is highly uncertain.
- The modal aerosol approach leads to lower aerosol perturbation from the cruise emission (e.g. NH₃NO₃ concentration in January) compared to previous studies using bulk approach for aerosol treatment.
- PM_{2.5} aviation-induced perturbations are less spatially dispersed compared to previous studies, which could have led to an overestimation of the number of premature deaths.

3.2.3 Inter-comparison study

Aerosol indirect effects on clouds, temperatures, photolysis, and mixing are the primary processes affecting modelled surface chemistry and PM_{2.5}. Cameron et al. (2017) make an effort to harmonize input data in order to objectively compare global simulation output from five different CTMs and CRMs models (Figure 3-3). The aircraft emissions data were taken from the 2006 AEDT global database (Wilkerson et al., 2010), which contain more than 30 million commercial aircraft flights. The authors make a distinction between CTMs and CRMs outputs. They found that compared to a reference case without aviation emission included, the simulations with aviation emission lead to an increase of the ground level PM₂₅ concentrations ranging from 0.14 to 0.4 % depending on the CTMs used while when using CRMs, the range varies from -1.9 % (a decrease) to an increase of 1.2 %.

The older simulations are very sensitive to aerosol background concentration level as well as feedbacks between aircraft emissions and selected meteorology fields. However, the output of later simulations demonstrates the existence of a strong interaction between natural and aviation aerosol emissions and meteorology. Hence, the response of the two types of models depends on whether models simulate two-way chemistry-meteorology feedbacks or one-way. CTM are less expensive than CRM but do not capture interactions between emissions and circulation (Wilcox et al., 2012).

Table 2. Change in O₃ and PM_{2.5}, and Background AOD^a

Model	Average Ozone (ppbv)	Average PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³)	Background AOD ^b
GATOR-GCMOM	0.045 (-2.5-4.9) 0.34%	0.0772 (-8.9-6.5) 0.42%	0.159
GEOS-5	(Replay) 0.52 (0.28-1.6) 1.92%	(GOCART) -0.17 (-1.8-2.3) -1.86%	0.091
NASA GISS ModelE2	0.17 (0.13-0.22) 0.53%	0.0062 (0.004-0.008) 0.42%	0.161
Fixed met. coupled	0.324 (-0.09-1.00) 1.15%	0.0165 (-0.015-0.071) 1.12%	--
CAM5	0.48 (0.32-0.67) 1.80%	0.0034 (0.0014-0.007) 0.21%	--
Fixed met.coupled	0.37 (0.12-0.83) 1.38%	0.0133 (-0.022-0.039) 1.18%	--
GEOS-Chem	0.43 (0.27-0.65) 1.63%	0.0070 (0.0018-0.014) 0.14%	0.121

^aO₃ and PM_{2.5} changes are due to the effects of 2006 aviation emissions relative to an atmosphere with no aviation emissions. Values are 2006 annual global averages, with monthly averaged minimum and maximum values in parentheses. Relative change (%) in the global, annual value is shown for average ozone and PM_{2.5}.

^bGlobal average clear-sky aerosol optical depth (AOD) at 550 nm without aviation emissions. GEOS-Chem is total-sky AOD. MODIS satellite clear-sky AOD (2001-2005) is 0.176. Dashed lines indicate background AOD values are not available.

Figure 3-3 Change in O₃ and PM_{2.5} linked to the different model configurations used in Cameron et al. (2017).

Main outcomes:

- Annual change in surface-level PM2.5 are 0.14 to 0.4 % for CTMs and -1.9 to 1.2 % for CRM.
- The feedback mechanisms, if implemented in the codes, lead to a change in surface particle concentrations due to natural background aerosol changes and not aviation emissions.
- Study of the impact of cruise emissions on ground level air quality should certainly be performed using two-way meteorology-chemistry numerical models.
- Background conditions or population composition are necessary to assess the health impact of cruise aviation emissions.
- Future work should use preferably regional modelling, as one major limitation of global simulation is the coarse vertical resolution that is likely to affect diffusion of emissions from cruise level to the surface; this is in agreement with Whitt et al. (2011) recommendations.
- Resolving both global and plume-scale effects could reduce some of the uncertainties.

3.3 Exhaust dynamics

The exhaust of an aircraft engine enters the free atmosphere with excess momentum, temperature, and turbulence. In addition, it interacts with the flow around the moving aircraft body. This exhaust dynamics has an impact on the concentration distribution of the pollutants emitted with the exhaust. In the near field, exhaust dynamics impacts the near-ground concentration by a factor of 2 or more (Barrett et al., 2013), farther away from the airport, it becomes less relevant, see Figure 3-4 for a generic example. Hence, it is important to understand the effects of exhaust dynamics on the plume dilution and plume transport, and to define appropriate parametrisations for given models and model purposes.

Figure 3-4 Test calculation (Janicke, 2021) with the dispersion model LASPORT to demonstrate the general effect of exhaust dynamics on near-ground concentration. The graphs show the near-ground concentration distribution (monthly average for February 2012) of SO₂ due to the emissions from aircraft main engines at Los Angeles International Airport.

Estimating plume dilution of aircraft exhaust is challenging. In the near field of the engine exit, entrainment is governed by density and velocity differences between the exhaust and ambient air, and the evolution can be described by a plume model (plume regime). In the far field, where density and velocity differences have levelled out, entrainment is governed by atmospheric turbulence as described by ordinary dispersion models (diffusion regime). The situation is complicated by the fact that the exhaust plumes from the engines of the aircraft begin to overlap at some distance behind the aircraft. And, for a moving aircraft, the air flow around the aircraft interacts with the exhaust flow, for example by wing vortex interaction.

Plume induced turbulence and buoyancy effects tend to decrease the near ground concentration. The horizontal momentum tends to shift the concentration in the horizontal. Wing-vortex interaction can shift the plume downwards and cause increased concentration peaks on a time scale of minutes, while it is likely of less relevance on a time scale of hours or more. In general, plume dynamics tends to reduce the concentration near ground and tend to reduce the dependency of concentration on ambient wind speed.

The farther away from the airport, the more ordinary atmospheric dispersion dominates and the less relevant the influence of initial plume dynamics becomes. For longer time averages of days or weeks, where many individual plumes of different aircrafts and wind directions overlap, the horizontal spread due to plume dynamics levels out and the effects of the vertical distribution of concentration become more relevant.

There are different approaches to account for plume dynamics in a dispersion calculation for aircraft emissions. Some put emphasis on thermal plume rise (e.g. Barrett et al., 2013), some on enhanced dynamical mixing (e.g. Janicke, 2008). Both approaches and combinations of them allow provisions of more realistic modelling of pollutant concentration from aircraft emissions. Ignoring plume dynamics in the dispersion calculation yields concentrations that are usually too high up to distances of a few kilometres from the airport.

When including an explicit thermal plume rise in the dispersion calculation with a lift-off of the plume from the ground, one should be sure that the modelling approach reflects real conditions sufficiently well in order not to unintentionally underestimate the near-ground concentration. When using Briggs-like formulas, care must be taken that the underlying assumptions and simplifications are valid. The plume-induced spreading of the exhaust should also be accounted for.

Any modelling approach applied to account for plume dynamics requires suitable measurement data for calibration and validation. The level of detail of the parametrisation and the required accuracy depends on the model capabilities and on the modelling purpose.

3.4 Particulate matter transformation

The number of non-volatile particles (nvPM) emitted from aircraft engines (mainly soot) can be assumed in a good approximation to not undergo transformation processes during atmospheric transport on a local scale of up to several 10 kilometres. Thus, nvPM number can be modelled to a good approximation as a passive tracer without transformation. The mass of

nvPM particles may change during atmospheric transport due to coating with other material, but mass of nvPM, which is in the UFP range, is usually very small compared to PM₁₀ from other sources and not of major interest.

Accounting for volatile particles (vPM) in local atmospheric dispersion modelling is more challenging. The volatile particles are not emitted, but they are created during transport. They also undergo complex changes in diameter (condensation and growth of the particles, re-evaporation) and number (formation of nuclei, agglomeration), particularly during the first second (nucleation) and minute (before dilution takes over) of atmospheric transport.

In the simplest approach, vPM can be included in a dispersion calculation by means of an effective emission rate (number and mass), see for example the method FOA4 in ICAO document 9889 for vPM mass. Such an emission rate implicitly refers to a typical transport time or distance from the engine where it is valid. For vPM number, this approach is probably not well suited in the near field (up to some 100 m from the engine), given the non-monotonous change of vPM number.

A more sophisticated approach would be to account for the formation and change of vPM number and mass by suitable transformation rates of vPM, for example between different diameter ranges. Besides defining realistic rates depending on engine power setting, exhaust gas properties and ambient conditions, a challenge is to account for the dynamics of both mass and number in such an approach.

4 Regulation

Different regulations are set by authorities to prevent and mitigate the health impact of particulate matter. Emission sources are regulated by standards decided at international and European level, while air quality must comply with EU Directives and national laws on ambient air and workplace exposure.

4.1 Emissions

Air traffic is not the only particulate matter source in the airport area. Diesel vehicles working inside the apron, such as aircraft handling operations, generators and road vehicles contribute to the increase in particulate matter concentration. Emission limits for aircraft engines and for road vehicles regulate both the mass and the number of particles emitted. Regarding the indoor concentration in the terminal buildings, particulate matter concentration is influenced by other sources, such as restaurant activities, which emit small particles in high numbers.

4.1.1 Aircraft related emissions: ICAO engine emissions regulation

Turbofan and Turbojet engine emissions are regulated by ICAO in the Annex 16 Volume II (ICAO, 2017). The different particle standards defined during the years are reported below.

4.1.1.1 Smoke Number

When the first Turbofan and turbojet engine emission limits were set in 1981, the focus was only on gaseous pollutants (NO_x, CO, HC) and on visible smoke. With the introduction of the

“smoke number” standard, black smoke in the exhaust gases was further restricted. This standard is applicable from 1981 until 2023 for engines with a rated output >26.7kN, while it will remain applicable after 2023 for engines with a rated output < 26.7kN. As a result of this standard, engine exhausts became cleaner, and particles emitted smaller.

The smoke number (SN) is calculated as follow:

$$SN = 100 * (1 - R_s / R_w)$$

Where R_w and R_s are the absolute reflectance of the clean filter material and the stained filter, respectively.

The regulatory limit is a function of the rated thrust F_{00} :

$$\text{Regulatory smoke number} = \min(83.6 * (F_{00})^{-0.274}, 50).$$

SN does not allow the assessment of particulate matter concentration without certain assumptions.

4.1.1.2 CAEP/10 standard

The first nvPM standard was agreed at the ICAO level in 2016 during the CAEP/10 meeting. While it is still a visibility-based standard that uses a mass concentration limit, it sets a limit to the particles emitted by the engine during the LTO cycle. This standard does not add any stringency with respect to the smoke number standard, as during its development it was assured that all engines complying with the smoke number standard would also comply with the CAEP/10 standard (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2016). It applies to all in-production engine types of rated thrust greater than 26.7 kN after 1st January 2020.

With the introduction of the CAEP/10 nvPM standard, engine manufacturers are obliged to report the nvPM mass and number emission indices for the four LTO points and the Maximum nvPM emission indices both for mass concentration and particulate number concentration.

The limit value is a function of the engine rated thrust, and it is given by the following formula:

$$\text{Limit } (\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3) = 10^{(3 + 2.9 * \text{thrust}^{-0.274})}$$

4.1.1.3 CAEP/11 Standard

CAEP/11 announced in 2019 the end of the smoke number standard applicability from the 1st January 2023 for engines with rated thrust greater than 26.7 kN. Data available from the CAEP/10 standard allowed the definition of a new LTO-based nvPM mass and number metric system, called CAEP/11 standard. The new standard will apply to new type and in-production engines from 1st January 2023 and introduces a new stringency with respect to the previous standard. There are two different limits, one for in-production engine types and the second for new engine types. The limits in this case are not on the concentration but on the mass and number emissions with respect to the rated thrust, thereby regulating the ultrafine particles as well. Another important achievement of this standard is the introduction of a standardized measurement method to account for the small particle losses during measurement.

Indicator	Standard	Rated Thrust	Limit
nvPM Mass Metric Value (mg/kN)	In-Production	< 200 kN	$\frac{(3725.4 * (thrust - 200))}{-173.3} + 347.5$
		≥ 200 kN	347.5
	New types	< 150 kN	$\frac{(852.5 * (thrust - 150))}{-123.3} + 214.5$
		≥ 150 kN	214.0
nvPM Number Metric Value (1/kN)	In-Production	< 200 kN	$\frac{(1.95 * 10^{16} * (thrust - 200))}{-173.3} + 4.17 * 10^{15}$
		≥ 200 kN	$4.17 * 10^{15}$
	New types	< 150 kN	$\frac{(9.92 * 10^{15} * (thrust - 150))}{-123.3} + 2.78 * 10^{15}$
		≥ 150 kN	$2.78 * 10^{15}$

Table 4-1 CAEP/11 nvPM limits.

4.1.2 Non-Aircraft related emissions: European regulations

4.1.2.1 Non-road diesel vehicles

Vehicles used for handling and loading in the airport must comply with the EU directive for non-road vehicles. According to the year in which they were placed into the market, non-road diesel vehicles should comply with 5 more stringent limit values, known as “Stage I” to “Stage V”. The first 4 tiers are included in the directive 97/68/EC (EU, 1997), while “Stage V”, the tier currently in place, was introduced in Regulation 2016/1628 (EU, 2016). These directives set limits for gaseous pollutants (CO, HC, NO_x) and particulate matter. “Stage V” regulates both particles mass and particles number emissions for both diesel and positive ignition engines, while the first four only regulate the particulate mass for diesel engines. In “Stage V”, for gaseous pollutants, different limit values are set according to the power of the engine, while for particulate matter, no distinction is made. Table 4-2 below summarizes which engine belongs to each power category and the corresponding particulate matter standards (Airports Council International, 2018):

Non-road engine	Stage	Date	PN (g/km)	PN (1/km)	Examples
NRE-v/c-4 (Diesel) 37 ≤ P < 56 kW	Stage V	2019	0.015	1x10 ¹²	Baggage Belt, Ramp Snake
NRE-v/c-5 (All) 56 ≤ P < 130 kW	Stage V	2020	0.015	1x10 ¹²	GPU, High Loader, Catering Truck
NRE-v/c-6 (All) 130 ≤ P < 560 kW	Stage V	2019	0.015	1x10 ¹²	Aircraft push-back tractor

Table 4-2 "Stage V" limits for non-road engine.

4.1.2.2 Road vehicles

Current standards are the so called “European Emissions Standards”. A distinction is made between light vehicles, regulated by Directive 70/220/EEC and amendments, and heavy-duty diesel vehicles, regulated by directive 88/7/EEC and consolidated by Directive 2005/55/EC. Both directives have 6 more stringent stages, called “EURO 1” to “EURO 6” for light vehicles and “EURO I” to “EURO VI” for heavy-duty diesel vehicles. Particle mass limits were added in “EURO 1” and “EURO I” for diesel light vehicles and heavy-duty diesel vehicles respectively, while in “EURO 5” for positive ignition light vehicles. Current limits (“EURO 6” for light vehicles, “EURO VI” for heavy-duty vehicles) regulate both particle mass and number of particles emitted by a vehicle and are presented in the Table 4-3 below (Airports Council International, 2018):

Vehicle type	Stage	Date	PM (g/km)	PM (1/km)	Comments
Passenger cars (Diesel)	EURO 6	09.2014	0.005	6.0x10 ⁻¹¹	0.0045 g/km using PMP measurement procedure
Passenger cars (Gasoline)	EURO 6	09.2014	0.005	6.0x10 ⁻¹¹	Applicable only to engines using DI engines; 0.0045 g/km using PMP measurement procedure
Light duty vehicles (Diesel), all classes	EURO 6	09.2015	0.005	6.0x10 ⁻¹¹	0.0045 g/kg using PMP measurement procedure
Light duty vehicles (Gasoline), all classes	EURO 6	09.2015	0.005	6.9x10 ⁻¹¹	Applicable only to engines using DI engines; 0.0045 g/km using PMP measurement procedure
Heavy duty vehicles (Diesel)	EURO VI	01.2013	0.01	8.0x10 ⁻¹¹	Steady-state testing
Heavy duty vehicles (Diesel)	EURO VI	01.2013	0.01	6.0x10 ⁻¹¹	Transient testing

Table 4-3 EURO 6 and EURO VI limits for light and heavy vehicles.

4.2 Ambient concentration

4.2.1 EU directives and WHO recommendations

In Europe, the concentration of pollutants in ambient air, including PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀, is regulated by the directive 2008/50/EC, (EU, 2008), which imposes Member States to not exceed certain pollutant concentration, although each country could also decide to introduce more stringent limits. With this directive, Member States are required to divide the territory in agglomerations where a minimum assessment of the air quality is required, such as continuous monitoring and air quality modelling. Data are reported on the European Commission website⁴.

In September 2021, WHO published the *Global Air Quality Guidelines (AQGs)*, recommending concentration limit values for particulate matter (PM), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and carbon monoxide (CO) (WHO, 2021). WHO warns that these concentrations are not a guaranty of safety for health for all the population and adds that the lowest concentration possible in the context of local constraints, capabilities and public health priorities should be reached. In comparison with the previous 2005 version, lower AQGs levels have been defined. This is due to an increasing awareness and research development on the relation between air quality and risks to health.

Table 4-4 summarizes recommended limit values proposed by WHO and the limit values set by EU.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/air/quality/zones.htm>

Pollutant	Averaging period	WHO recommended limit values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	EU 2008/50/EC Directive limits ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
UFP	-	No recommendation	Not regulated
PM2.5	24-hour average	15 ^a	Not regulated
	1-year average	5	20
PM10	24-hour average	45 ^a	50 ^b
	1-year average	15	40

^a 99th percentile (i.e., 3-4 exceedance days per year)

^b Permitted exceedance per year: 35

Table 4-4 WHO guidelines and EU limits for particulate matter concentration.

In addition to the guideline values shown in Table 4-4, the WHO *Global air quality guidelines* provide also interim targets for concentrations of PM10 and PM2.5 aimed at promoting a gradual shift to lower concentrations leading to obtain significant reductions in risks for acute and chronic health effects.

Recommendations in terms of ultrafine particles (UFP) are not provided due to insufficient data from epidemiology field. However, it is proved that UFP lead to significative health issues: as consequence, WHO indicates good practice statements for that pollutant. In particular, these statements are summarized as follow:

1. Defining UFP as particle number concentration (PNC) for a size range ≤ 10 nm;
2. Integrating UFP in the common air quality monitoring strategy e.g., implementing real-time PNC measurements at certain air monitoring stations;
3. Distinguish between low⁵ and high PNC to guide decisions on the priorities of UFP source emission control;
4. Exploiting technology to advance the assessment of exposure to UFP.

EU directive 2008/50/EC adds additional PM2.5 objectives set at national level based on the average exposure indicator (AEI). This indicator is the PM2.5 value determined as a three-calendar year running annual mean averaged over selected monitoring zones and agglomerations throughout the territory of a Member State. To reduce PM2.5 exposure, the directive sets two limits, one binding from 2015, 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$; the second, set at national level, requires achieving, where possible, a limit equal to 18 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ minus a coefficient dependent on the 2010 AEI level.

4.3 Indoor and workplace

4.3.1 Workplace

While the apron area is regulated by EU Directive 2008/50/EC as it is an outdoor environment, pollutant concentrations in indoor workplaces are regulated by EU Directive 89/654/EEC (EU, 1989) on the minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace. This directive requires that in indoor workplaces sufficient fresh air in enclosed workplaces should be available, considering the working methods used and the physical demands placed on the

⁵ Low PNC can be considered 10,000 1/cm³ (24-hour mean) or 20,000 1/cm³ (1-hour).

workers. For this reason, it can be concluded that in indoor workplaces air quality should comply with EU Directive 2008/50/EC⁶.

In general, as workers spend a limited time in their workplace and could be exposed to hazardous chemical substances, European Union adds additional limits, known as Occupational Exposure Limits, to protect the health of workers. Six directives are regulating the occupational exposure limits to pollutants: 91/322/CEE, 2000/39/EC, 2006/15/EC, 2009/161/EU, 2017/164, 2019/1831. These directives establish specific limit values for some chemical components. No occupational exposure limit is currently proposed for particulate matter at EU level, but some countries, as part of national Health and Safety regulations, are already regulating occupational exposure limits for this pollutant as well.

An example is Denmark, which sets an 8-hour workplace limit value for both coarse and fine particles (Press-Kristensen and Økologiske Råd, 2012). In addition, to protect the health of workers exposed to diesel engine exhaust emissions, which have risks related to the exposure to carcinogens or mutagens, EU Directive 2019/130 introduced an 8-hour limit value, equal to 0.05 mg/m³ measured as elemental carbon. This limit will be introduced on the 21st February 2023 (21st February 2026 for underground mining and tunnel construction) (EU, 2019).

Regarding the air quality in the airport's workplaces, of particular interest is the apron, as it is directly exposed to aircraft and vehicles emissions. Several studies highlight that during the day the airport area seems to be characterized by a higher number of small particles compared to urban areas, while gaseous pollutants concentrations seem to be similar. A study conducted at Copenhagen airport found that gaseous pollutant concentrations in the apron are similar to concentrations measured in major roads inside the city, but the PM number is 2-3 times higher than in the city centre and characterized by a very small diameter (Ellermann et al., 2012).

Moreover, the majority of these particles were ultrafine particles, expected to originate from jet engines, APUs, and diesel engines of service vehicles. A more recent study conducted at Heathrow proved that, in general, gaseous pollutant concentrations at the airport border are similar to that measured inside the city of London, while particles during the day are characterized by smaller diameters and higher concentrations, associated with aircraft operations (Stacey et al., 2020).

4.3.2 Indoor air quality

Currently no specific EU directive is regulating indoor air quality (Settimo et al., 2020). Limits are set by each member state as part of national regulations. 2010 WHO Guidelines for indoor air quality mentions that particulate matter limits recommended in the 2005 outdoor guidelines are also applicable indoor, while for other pollutants (Benzene, Carbon monoxide, Nitrogen oxide and others), specific indoor recommended limit values are proposed (WHO, 2010). Some EU countries have started to develop reference values for indoor air quality, taking into consideration WHO reference guidelines, national plans, and making mandatory indoor air quality monitoring. In addition, the International Standards Organization (ISO) developed the specific standard, "EN ISO 16000: Indoor air", which gives advise on how to analyse the main indoor pollutants (Settimo et al., 2020).

⁶ [https://oshwiki.eu/wiki/Indoor_air_quality_\(IAQ\)](https://oshwiki.eu/wiki/Indoor_air_quality_(IAQ))

In any case, air quality inside airport buildings seems to be characterized by less ultrafine particles concentration compared to the apron area. A study conducted at Copenhagen airport found that apron workers, such as baggage handlers, are exposed to ultrafine particle concentrations seven times higher than people working indoors (35'000 particles/cm³ vs 5'000 particles/cm³), while catering drivers, cleaning staff and airstaff security are exposed to intermediate concentrations (on average, 15'000 particles/cm³). This difference is due to the different amount of time spent indoor or on the apron (Møller et al., 2020). In the last years some studies have started to analyse the air quality of buildings inside and near the airport area. Two study conducted at Zurich and Bologna airports show how ventilation systems and filters are effective in preventing particulate matter from migrating indoors from the apron, reducing the concentration by more than 90%.

Indoor ultrafine particle concentration does not seem to be influenced by airside operations, as its concentration remains almost constant during the day. It is however influenced by indoor activities, in particular, food preparation (Zurich Airport, 2019; Zanni et al., 2018). Residential areas around the airports could also be influenced by ultrafine particles coming from the airport itself.

A recent study conducted at Logan airport in Boston (US) suggests that airport activities can influence indoor ultrafine particles concentration in residential areas situated up to 4 km downwind from the airports. In this study, it is shown how indoor concentration is higher when the wind blows from the airport towards the residential areas than with any other wind direction (Hudda et al., 2018). The study highlights how similar impacts could be found around other airports as well.

4.4 Outlook

Current gaps in the regulation of aircraft-related emission sources need to be evaluated in more detail in the future. In addition, there is no aircraft engine emission standard for vPM, which should also be considered with attention. Regarding air quality regulations for indoor and workplaces, currently there is no EU Directive specifically on particulate matter, and Member States have started to develop their own national regulations with different working groups (Settimo et al., 2020).

The absence of an occupational exposure limit for PM and ultrafine particles could be of particular relevance as ultrafine particle concentration in the apron during the air traffic's activities is high compared to background and urban areas. For ambient air concentration, there is no regulation on ultrafine particles.

In polluted environments, such as urban areas, number of particles are about one order of magnitude higher than in clean environments, for this reason future standard should target a reduction of one order of magnitude (Morawska et al., 2019). Mitigating particle mass by setting a limit on the concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ doesn't lead to a reduction of ultrafine particles, while mitigating black carbon emissions won't remove all the ultrafine particles from combustion sources (Morawska et al., 2019). This suggests that, to address the ultrafine particles impact on human health, regulatory approaches and control measures specifically for this pollutant should be used.

5 Literature

- Abid, A.D., Heinz, N., Tolmachoff, E.D., Phares, D.J., Campbell, C.S., Wang, H., 2008. On evolution of particle size distribution functions of incipient soot in premixed ethylene-oxygen-argon flames. *Combustion and Flame* 154, 775–788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2008.06.009>
- Agarwal, A., Speth, R.L., Fritz, T.M., Jacob, S.D., Rindlisbacher, T., Iovinelli, R., Owen, B., Miake-Lye, R.C., Sabnis, J.S., Barrett, S.R.H., 2019. SCOPE11 Method for Estimating Aircraft Black Carbon Mass and Particle Number Emissions. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53, 1364–1373. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b04060>
- Airports Council International, 2018. Ultrafine particles at Airports - Current understanding of ultrafine particle emissions and concentrations at airports in 2018.
- Arunachalam, S., Valencia, A., Woody, M.C., Snyder, M.G., Huang, J., Weil, J., Soucacos, P., Webb, S., Airport Cooperative Research Program, Transportation Research Board, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2017. Dispersion Modeling Guidance for Airports Addressing Local Air Quality Health Concerns. Transportation Research Board, Washington, D.C. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24881>
- Barone, A.C., D'Alessio, A., D'Anna, A., 2003. Morphological characterization of the early process of soot formation by atomic force microscopy. *Combustion and Flame* 132, 181–187. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180\(02\)00434-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180(02)00434-0)
- Barrett, S.R.H., Britter, R.E., Waitz, I.A., 2013. Impact of aircraft plume dynamics on airport local air quality. *Atmospheric Environment* 74, 247–258. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2013.03.061>
- Barrett, S.R.H., Britter, R.E., Waitz, I.A., 2010. Global mortality attributable to aircraft cruise emissions. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 44, 7736–7742. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es101325r>
- Bergthorson, J.M., Thomson, M.J., 2015. A review of the combustion and emissions properties of advanced transportation biofuels and their impact on existing and future engines. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 42, 1393–1417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.10.034>
- Bisson, J., Seers, P., Huegel, M., Garnier, F., 2016. Numerical prediction of gaseous aerosol precursors and particles in an aircraft engine. *Journal of Propulsion and Power* 32, 918–928. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.B35943>
- Bulzan, D., Anderson, B., Wey, C., Howard, R., Winstead, E., Beyersdorf, A., Corporan, E., DeWitt, M.J., Klingshirn, C., Herndon, S., Miake-Lye, R., Timko, M., Wood, E., Tacina, K.M., Liscinsky, D., Hagen, D., Lobo, P., Whitefield, P., 2010. Gaseous and particulate emissions results of the NASA Alternative Aviation Fuel Experiment (AAFEX), in: Volume 2: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, Parts A and B. ASMEDC, pp. 1195–1207. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2010-23524>
- Cain, J., DeWitt, M.J., Blunck, D., Corporan, E., Striebich, R., Anneken, D., Klingshirn, C., Roquemore, W.M., Vander Wal, R., 2013. Characterization of Gaseous and Particulate Emissions From a Turbohaft Engine Burning Conventional, Alternative, and Surrogate Fuels. *Energy & Fuels* 27, 2290–2302. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef400009c>
- Cameron, M.A., Jacobson, M.Z., Barrett, S.R.H., Bian, H., Chen, C.C., Eastham, S.D., Gettelman, A., Khodayari, A., Liang, Q., Selkirk, H.B., Unger, N., Wuebbles, D.J., Yue, X., 2017. An intercomparative study of the effects of aircraft emissions on surface air

- quality: Effects of Aircraft on Surface AQ. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* 122, 8325–8344. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JD025594>
- Cavaliere, A., Barbella, R., Ciajolo, A., D'anna, A., Ragucci, R., 1994. Fuel and soot oxidation in diesel-like conditions. *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 25, 167–174. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(06\)80641-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(06)80641-7)
- Chan, T.W., Pham, V., Chalmers, J., Davison, C., Chishty, W., Poitras, P., 2013. Immediate impacts on particulate and gaseous emissions from a T56 turbo-prop engine using a biofuel blend, in: *SAE Technical Paper Series, SAE Technical Paper Series*. SAE International 400 Commonwealth Drive, Warrendale, PA, United States. <https://doi.org/10.4271/2013-01-2131>
- Chati, Y., Balakrishnan, H., 2014. Analysis of Aircraft Fuel Burn and Emissions in the Landing and Take Off Cycle using Operational Data. Presented at the International Conference on Research in Air Transportation, Istanbul.
- Chen, Y., Lee, W., Uang, S., Lee, S., Tsai, P., 2006. Characteristics of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon (PAH) emissions from a UH-1H helicopter engine and its impact on the ambient environment. *Atmospheric Environment* 40, 7589–7597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2006.06.054>
- Cheng, M.-D., Corporan, E., DeWitt, M., Landgraf, B., 2009. Emissions of volatile particulate components from turboshaft engines operated with JP-8 and Fischer-Tropsch Fuels. *Aerosol and Air Quality Research* 237–256.
- Cheng, M.-D., Corporan, E., DeWitt, M.J., Spicer, C.W., Holdren, M.W., Cowen, K.A., Laskin, A., Harris, D.B., Shores, R.C., Kagann, R., Hashmonay, R., 2008. Probing emissions of military cargo aircraft: description of a joint field measurement Strategic Environmental Research and Development Program. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association (1995)* 58, 787–796. <https://doi.org/10.3155/1047-3289.58.6.787>
- Corporan, E., DeWitt, M.J., Belovich, V., Pawlik, R., Lynch, A.C., Gord, J.R., Meyer, T.R., 2007. Emissions Characteristics of a Turbine Engine and Research Combustor Burning a Fischer-Tropsch Jet Fuel. *Energy & Fuels* 21, 2615–2626. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef070015j>
- Corporan, E., DeWitt, M.J., Klingshirn, C.D., Striebich, R., Cheng, M.-D., 2010. Emissions Characteristics of Military Helicopter Engines with JP-8 and Fischer-Tropsch Fuels. *Journal of Propulsion and Power* 26, 317–324. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.43928>
- Corporan, E., Monroig, O., Wagner, M., DeWitt, M.J., 2004. Influence of Fuel Chemical Composition on Particulate Matter Emissions of a Turbine Engine, in: *Volume 1: Turbo Expo 2004*. ASME/EDC, pp. 837–848. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2004-54335>
- Corporan, E., Quick, A., DeWitt, M.J., 2008. Characterization of particulate matter and gaseous emissions of a C-130H aircraft. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association (1995)* 58, 474–483. <https://doi.org/10.3155/1047-3289.58.4.474>
- Crayford, A., Johnson, M., 2011. SAMPLE III: Contribution to aircraft engine PM certification requirement and standard: First specific contract -final report, Studying, sampling, and measuring aircraft particulate emissions III- Specific Contract 01. European Aviation Safety Agency, Cologne Germany.
- Czyż, Z., Grabowski, L., Pietrykowski, K., Czarnigowski, J., Porzak, M., 2018. Measurement of flight parameters in terms of toxic emissions of the aircraft radial engine ASz62-IR. *Measurement* 113, 46–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2017.08.035>

- Dellaert, S.N.C., Hulskotte, J.H.J., 2017. Emissions of air pollutants from civil aviation in the Netherlands (No. TNO 2017 R10055). Utrecht.
- Dellinger, N., Bertier, N., Dupoirieux, F., Legros, G., 2020. Hybrid Eulerian-Lagrangian method for soot modelling applied to ethylene-air premixed flames. *Energy* 194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2019.116858>
- DfT, U., 2006. Project for the Sustainable Development of Heathrow (PSDH).
- Dobbins, R.A., 2002. Soot inception temperature and the carbonization rate of precursor particles. *Combustion and Flame* 130, 204–214. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180\(02\)00374-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180(02)00374-7)
- Dorey, L.H., Bertier, N., Tessé, L., Dupoirieux, F., 2011. Soot and radiation modeling in laminar ethylene flames with tabulated detailed chemistry. *Comptes Rendus - Mécanique* 339, 756–769. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crme.2011.09.004>
- Drozd, G.T., Miracolo, M.A., Presto, A.A., Lipsky, E.M., Riemer, D.D., Corporan, E., Robinson, A.L., 2012. Particulate Matter and Organic Vapor Emissions from a Helicopter Engine Operating on Petroleum and Fischer–Tropsch Fuels. *Energy & Fuels* 26, 4756–4766. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ef300651t>
- Duchene, N., Celikel, A., Fuller, I., Silue, M., Fleuti, E., Hofmann, P., Moore, T., 2004. Airport Local Air Quality Studies Case Study: Emission Inventory for Zurich Airport with different methodologies (No. 10), EEC/SEE.
- Durdina, L., Brem, B.T., Schönenberger, D., Siegerist, F., Anet, J.G., Rindlisbacher, T., 2019. Nonvolatile Particulate Matter Emissions of a Business Jet Measured at Ground Level and Estimated for Cruising Altitudes. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 53, 12865–12872. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b02513>
- Eberle, C., Gerlinger, P., Aigner, M., 2017. Large Eddy Simulations of a Sooting Lifted Turbulent, in: 55th AIAA Aerospace Sciences Meeting. pp. 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2017-1785>
- EC, 2019. Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council.
- EC, 2016. Directive (EU) 2016/2284 of the European Parliament and of the Council.
- EC, 2011. Flightpath 2050 :Europe’s vision for aviation : maintaining global leadership and serving society’s needs. Publications Office, LU.
- ECE, 2014. Guidelines for Reporting Emissions and Projections Data under the Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution (No. ECE/EB.AIR/125). Economic Commission for Europe.
- EEA, 2017. Air quality in Europe: 2017 report. Publications Office, LU.
- EEA, 2013. 7th Environment Action Programme — European Environment Agency [WWW Document]. URL <https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/7th-environmental-action-programme> (accessed 9.5.21).
- EEDB, 2021. ICAO Engine Emission Databank. hosted by the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA).
- Ellermann, T., Massling, A., Løfstrøm, P., Winther, M., Nøjgaard, J., Ketzel, M., 2012. Assessment of the air quality at the apron of Copenhagen Airport Kastrup in relation to the working environment. Aarhus University, Department for Environmental Science.
- EMEP/EEA, 2019. Air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2019 - Aviation.
- EU, 2019. DIRECTIVE (EU) 2019/ 130 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL - of 16 January 2019 - amending Directive 2004/ 37/ EC on the

- protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work, Official Journal of the European Union L 30/112 9.
- EU, 2016. REGULATION (EU) 2016/1628 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 14 September 2016 on requirements relating to gaseous and particulate pollutant emission limits and type-approval for internal combustion engines for non-road mobile machinery, amending Regulations (EU) No 1024/2012 and (EU) No 167/2013, and amending and repealing Directive 97/68/EC [2016], Official Journal of the European Union L 252/53. Hart Publishing.
- EU, 2008. Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2004 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe . Official Journal of the European Union L152/1.
- EU, 1997. DIRECTIVE 97/68/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 December 1997 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to measures against the emission of gaseous and particulate pollutants from internal combustion engines to be installed in non-road mobile machinery [1997], Official Journal of the European Communities L 59/1.
- EU, 1989. COUNCIL DIRECTIVE of 30 November 1989 concerning the minimum safety and health requirements for the workplace (first individual directive within the meaning of Article 16 (1) of Directive 89/ 391 /EEC), [1989], Official Journal of the European Communities No L 393/1.
- Fleuti, E., Hofmann, P., 2005. Aircraft APU-Emissions at Zurich Airport. Unique Flughafen Zürich AG.
- Fleuti, E., Maraini, S., 2012. Air Quality Assessment Sensitivities: Zurich Airport Case Study. Flughafen Zürich AG.
- FOCA, 2007a. FOCA database for aircraft piston engine emission factors: Appendix 2: In-flight measurements. Switzerland Federal Office of Aviation.
- FOCA, 2007b. Aircraft piston engine emissions: Appendix 4: Nanoparticle measurements and research for cleaner AVGAS. Switzerland Federal Office of Aviation, Switzerland.
- FOCA, 2007c. Aircraft piston engine emissions: Appendix 3: Power settings and procedures for static ground measurements. Switzerland Federal Office of Aviation, FOCA.
- Frenklach, M., Clary, D.W., Gardiner, W.C., Stein, S.E., 1985. Detailed kinetic modeling of soot formation in shock-tube pyrolysis of acetylene. Symposium (International) on Combustion 20, 887–901. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(85\)80578-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(85)80578-6)
- Frenklach, M., Wang, H., 1994. Detailed Mechanism and Modeling of Soot Particle Formation, in: Bockhorn, H. (Ed.), Soot Formation and Combustion. Springer-Verlag, pp. 165–190.
- Frenklach, M., Wang, H., 1991. Detailed modeling of soot particle nucleation and growth. Symposium (International) on Combustion 23, 1559–1566. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(06\)80426-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(06)80426-1)
- Frenklach, M., Warnatz, J., 1987. Detailed modeling of PAH profiles in a sooting low pressure acetylene flame. Combustion Science and Technology 51, 265–283.
- Fuller, I.A., Celikel, A., 2005. Airport Local Air Quality Studies, ALAQS Case Study: Zurich Airport 2004, a comparison of modelled and measured air quality. EEC/SEE. https://doi.org/10.1163/1570-6664_iyb_SIM_org_39214
- Gallen, L., 2020. Prediction of soot particles in Gas Turbine Combustors using Large Eddy Simulation (PhD Thesis). Toulouse University.

- Gauderman, W.J., Avol, E., Gilliland, F., Vora, H., Thomas, D., Berhane, K., McConnell, R., Kuenzli, N., Lurmann, F., Rappaport, E., Margolis, H., Bates, D., Peters, J., 2004. The Effect of Air Pollution on Lung Development from 10 to 18 Years of Age. *New England Journal of Medicine* 351, 1057–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa040610>
- Habre, R., Zhou, H., Eckel, S.P., Enebish, T., Fruin, S., Bastain, T., Rappaport, E., Gilliland, F., 2018. Short-term effects of airport-associated ultrafine particle exposure on lung function and inflammation in adults with asthma. *Environ Int* 118, 48–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.05.031>
- Haynes, B.S., Wagner, H.G., 1982. The surface growth phenomenon in soot formation. *Zeitschrift fur Physikalische Chemie* 133, 201–213. <https://doi.org/10.1524/zpch.1982.133.2.201>
- Hofman, J., Staelens, J., Cordell, R., Stroobants, C., Zikova, N., Hama, S.M.L., Wyche, K.P., Kos, G.P.A., Van Der Zee, S., Smallbone, K.L., Weijers, E.P., Monks, P.S., Roekens, E., 2016. Ultrafine particles in four European urban environments: Results from a new continuous long-term monitoring network. *Atmospheric Environment* 136, 68–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.04.010>
- Hudda, N., Fruin, S.A., 2016. International Airport Impacts to Air Quality: Size and Related Properties of Large Increases in Ultrafine Particle Number Concentrations. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 50, 3362–3370. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.5b05313>
- Hudda, N., Simon, M.C., Zamore, W., Durant, J.L., 2018. Aviation-Related Impacts on Ultrafine Particle Number Concentrations Outside and Inside Residences near an Airport. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52, 1765–1772. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b05593>
- ICAO, 2020. ICAO Engine Exhaust Emissions Databank.
- ICAO, 2017. Annex 16 to the Convention on International Civil Aviation: Environmental Protection, Volume II: Aircraft Engine Emissions (4th Edition). International Civil Aviation Organisation.
- ICAO, 2014. ICAO, Volume 2, Appendix 7: Environmental Technical Manual, Procedures for the Emissions Certification of Aircraft Engines.
- ICAO-9889, 2020. ICAO document 9889: Airport Air Quality Manual, 2nd ed. International Civil Aviation Organisation.
- International Civil Aviation Organization, 2016. ICAO Environmental Report.
- International Civil Aviation Organization, 2010. ICAO Environmental Report.
- Janicke, U., 2008. Some aspects of LASPORT 2.0. OMEGA CONSORTIUM, International Conference on Airport Air Quality. Royal Aeronautical Society, London, 13-14 October.
- Janicke, U., 2005. Derivation of smooth & shift parameters to account for source dynamics in ALAQs-AV emission grids (No. 16), EEC/SEE. EUROCONTROL.
- Jerzy Merkisz, Jaroslaw Markowski, Jacek Pielecha, Maciej Babiak, 2010. Emission Measurements of the AI-14RA Aviation Engine in stationary test and under Real Operating Conditions of PZL-104 'Wilga' Plane. *SAE International Journal of Fuels and Lubricants* 507–520.
- Jerzy Merkisz, Markowski, J., Pielecha, J., Jasiński, R., 2014. Exhaust emissions measurements from a small airplane.
- Kärcher, B., Yu, F., 2009. Role of aircraft soot emissions in contrail formation. *Geophysical Research Letters* 36, L01804. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2008GL036649>

- Kennedy, I.M., 1997. Models of soot formation and oxidation. *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci* 23, 95–132.
- Keuken, M.P., Moerman, M., Zandveld, P., Henzing, J.S., Hoek, G., 2015. Total and size-resolved particle number and black carbon concentrations in urban areas near Schiphol airport (the Netherlands). *Atmospheric Environment* 104, 132–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.01.015>
- Khandelwal, B., Cronly, J., Ahmed, I.S., Wijesinghe, C.J., Lewis, C., 2019. The effect of alternative fuels on gaseous and particulate matter (PM) emission performance in an auxiliary power unit (APU). *The Aeronautical Journal* 123, 617–634. <https://doi.org/10.1017/aer.2019.16>
- Kim, B., Rachami, J., Robinson, D., Robinette, B., Wyle, K.N., Arunachalam, S., Davis, N., Baek, B.H., Shankar, U., Talgo, K., Yang, D., Hanna, A.F., Wayson, R.L., Noel, G., Gliff, S.S., Zhao, Y., Hopke, P.K., Kumar, P., Airport Cooperative Research Program, Transportation Research Board, National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine, 2012. Guidance for Quantifying the Contribution of Airport Emissions to Local Air Quality. Transportation Research Board, Washington, D.C. <https://doi.org/10.17226/22757>
- Kinsey, J.S., Corporan, E., Pavlovic, J., DeWitt, M., Klingshirn, C., Logan, R., 2019. Comparison of measurement methods for the characterization of the black carbon emissions from a T63 turboshaft engine burning conventional and Fischer-Tropsch fuels. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* (1995) 69, 576–591. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2018.1556188>
- Kinsey, J.S., Timko, M.T., Herndon, S.C., Wood, E.C., Yu, Z., Miake-Lye, R.C., Lobo, P., Whitefield, P., Hagen, D., Wey, C., Anderson, B.E., Beyersdorf, A.J., Hudgins, C.H., Thornhill, K.L., Winstead, E., Howard, R., Bulzan, D.I., Tacina, K.B., Knighton, W.B., 2012. Determination of the emissions from an aircraft auxiliary power unit (APU) during the Alternative Aviation Fuel Experiment (AAFEX). *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* (1995) 62, 420–430. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10473289.2012.655884>
- Klapmeyer, M.E., Marr, L.C., 2012. CO₂, NO_x, and particle emissions from aircraft and support activities at a regional airport. *Environmental science & technology* 46, 10974–10981. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es302346x>
- Koudis, G.S., Hu, S.J., Majumdar, A., Jones, R., Stettler, M.E.J., 2017. Airport emissions reductions from reduced thrust takeoff operations. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 52, 15–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2017.02.004>
- Kuenen, J., Dellaert, S., Visschedijk, A., Jalkanen, J.-P., Super, I., Denier van der Gon, H., 2021. CAMS-REG-v4: a state-of-the-art high-resolution European emission inventory for air quality modelling. *Earth System Science Data Discussions* 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-2021-242>
- Kuenen, J.J.P., Visschedijk, A.J.H., Jozwicka, M., Denier van der Gon, H.A.C., 2014. TNO-MACC_II emission inventory; a multi-year (2003–2009) consistent high-resolution European emission inventory for air quality modelling. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 14, 10963–10976. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-10963-2014>
- Kugele, A., Jelinek, F., Gaffal, R., 2005. Aircraft Particulate Matter Emission Estimation through all Phases of Flight. https://doi.org/10.1163/1570-6664_iyb_SIM_org_39214

- Lee, H., Olsen, S.C., Wuebbles, D.J., Youn, D., 2013. Impacts of aircraft emissions on the air quality near the ground. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 13, 5505–5522. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-13-5505-2013>
- Legros, G., Torero, J.L., 2015. Phenomenological model of soot production inside a non-buoyant laminar diffusion flame. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 35, 2545–2553. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2014.05.038>
- Leung, K.M., Lindstedt, R.P., Jones, W.P., 1991. A simplified reaction mechanism for soot formation in nonpremixed flames. *Combustion and Flame* 87, 289–305. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-2180\(91\)90114-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-2180(91)90114-Q)
- Liu, Y., Sun, X., Sethi, V., Nalianda, D., Li, Y.G., Wang, L., 2017. Review of modern low emissions combustion technologies for aero gas turbine engines, *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*. Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2017.08.001>
- Lobo, P., Christie, S., Khandelwal, B., Blakey, S.G., Raper, D.W., 2015. Evaluation of Non-volatile Particulate Matter Emission Characteristics of an Aircraft Auxiliary Power Unit with Varying Alternative Jet Fuel Blend Ratios. *Energy & Fuels* 29, 7705–7711. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.5b01758>
- Lukachko, S.P., Waitz, I.A., Miake-Lye, R.C., Brown, R.C., Anderson, M.R., 1998. Production of sulfate aerosol precursors in the turbine and exhaust nozzle of an aircraft engine. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 103, 16159–16174. <https://doi.org/10.1029/98JD00684>
- Magnussen, B.F., Hjertager, B.H., 1977. On mathematical modeling of turbulent combustion with special emphasis on soot formation and combustion. *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 16, 719–729. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(77\)80366-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(77)80366-4)
- Maraini, S., 2012. Sensitivity of Aircraft Operational Improvements: LAQ Modeling of Landing and Take-off Cycles. Flughafen Zürich AG.
- Masiol, M., Harrison, R.M., 2014. Aircraft engine exhaust emissions and other airport-related contributions to ambient air pollution: A review. *Atmospheric Environment* 95, 409–455. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.05.070>
- Mauss, F., Schäfer, T., Bockhorn, H., 1994. Inception and growth of soot particles in dependence on the surrounding gas phase. *Combustion and Flame* 99, 697–705. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-2180\(94\)90064-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0010-2180(94)90064-7)
- Møller, K.L., Brauer, C., Mikkelsen, S., Bonde, J.P., Loft, S., Helweg-Larsen, K., Thygesen, L.C., 2020. Cardiovascular disease and long-term occupational exposure to ultrafine particles: A cohort study of airport workers. *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 223, 214–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2019.08.010>
- Moore, R.H., Shook, M.A., Ziemba, L.D., DiGangi, J.P., Winstead, E.L., Rauch, B., Jurkat, T., Thornhill, K.L., Crosbie, E.C., Robinson, C., Shingler, T.J., Anderson, B.E., 2017. Take-off engine particle emission indices for in-service aircraft at Los Angeles International Airport. *Sci Data* 4, 170198. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.198>
- Morawska, L., Wierzbicka, A., Cyrus, J., Schnelle, J., Kowalski, M., Riediker, M., Birmili, W., Querol, X., Cassee, F.R., Yildirim, A.Ö., Yu, I.J., Øvrevik, J., Sørig, K., Loft, S., Schmid, O., Stöger, T., 2019. Ambient ultrafine particles: evidence for policy makers.
- Moss, J.B., 1994. Modelling Soot Formation for Turbulent Flame Prediction, in: Bockhorn, H. (Ed.), *Soot Formation and Combustion*. Springer-Verlag, pp. 551–568.
- Mueller, M. E., Blanquart, G., Pitsch, H., 2009a. A joint volume-surface-hydrogen multi-variate model for soot formation. *Combustion generated ne carbonaceous particles* 437–463.

- Mueller, M. E., Blanquart, G., Pitsch, H., 2009b. Hybrid Method of Moments for modeling soot formation and growth. *Combustion and Flame* 156, 1143–1155.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2009.01.025>
- Mueller, Michael Edward, Blanquart, G., Pitsch, H., 2009. A joint volume-surface model of soot aggregation with the method of moments. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 32 I, 785–792. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2008.06.207>
- Nguyen, T.H., Nguyen-Tri, P., Vancassel, X., Garnier, F., 2019. Aero-thermodynamic and chemical process interactions in an axial high-pressure turbine of aircraft engines. *International Journal of Engine Research* 20, 653–669.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1468087418772228>
- Padhra, A., 2018. Emissions from auxiliary power units and ground power units during intraday aircraft turnarounds at European airports. *Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment* 63, 433–444. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2018.06.015>
- Peck, J., Yu, Z., Miake-Lye, R.C., Liscinsky, D.S., 2016. A Volatile Particle Microphysical Simulation Model for the Evolution of Surrogate Organic Emissions in an Aircraft Exhaust Plume 6.
- Phoenix, D., Khodayari, A., Wuebbles, D., Stewart, K., 2019. Aviation impact on air quality present day and mid-century simulated in the Community Atmosphere Model (CAM). *Atmospheric Environment* 196, 125–132.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.10.005>
- Pitsch, H., 1996. Detailed kinetic reaction mechanism for ignition and oxidation of α -methylnaphthalene. *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 26, 721–728.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(96\)80280-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(96)80280-3)
- Press-Kristensen, K., Økologiske Råd, 2012. Air pollution in airports: ultrafine particles, solutions and successful cooperation. Danish Ecocouncil, Kbh.
- Rezy, B., Stuckas, K., Tucker, J., & Meyers, J., 1979. Concepts For Reducing Exhaust Emissions And Fuel Consumption Of The Aircraft Piston Engine. *SAE Transactions* 2109-2142.
- Rindlisbacher, T., 2007. Schadstoffemissionen von Flugzeug-Kolbenmotoren (No. 0 / 3/33/33-05-003 ECERT). FOCA.
- Rindlisbacher, T., Chabbey, L., 2015. Guidance on the Determination of Helicopter Emissions (No. COO.2207.111.2.2015750). FOCA.
- Rodrigues, P., 2018. Modélisation multiphysique de flammes turbulentes suitees avec la prise en compte des transferts radiatifs et des transferts de chaleur pariétaux (PhD Thesis). Toulouse university.
- Rodrigues, P., Franzelli, B., Vicquelin, R., Gicquel, O., Darabiha, N., 2018. Coupling an LES approach and a soot sectional model for the study of sooting turbulent non-premixed flames. *Combustion and Flame* 190, 477–499.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2017.12.009>
- Rogers, F., Arnott, P., Zielinska, B., Sagebiel, J., Kelly, K.E., Wagner, D., Lighty, J.S., Sarofim, A.F., 2005. Real-time measurements of jet aircraft engine exhaust. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* 55, 583–593.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10473289.2005.10464651>
- Ruf, C., 2013. Airport Local Air Quality: Zurich Airport Regional Air Quality Study 2013. Flughafen Zürich AG.
- S. J. Harris and A. M. Weiner, 1983. Surface growth of soot particles in premixed ethylene/air flames. *Combustion Science and Technology* 31, 155–167.

- Saffaripour, M., Veshkini, A., Kholghy, M., Thomson, M.J., 2014. Experimental investigation and detailed modeling of soot aggregate formation and size distribution in laminar coflow diffusion flames of Jet A-1, a synthetic kerosene, and n-decane. *Combustion and Flame* 161, 848–863. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.combustflame.2013.10.016>
- Schäfer, K., 2001. Non-Intrusive measurements of aircraft and rocket exhaust emissions. *Air & Space Europe* 3, 104–108. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1290-0958\(01\)90027-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1290-0958(01)90027-9)
- Scott Research laboratory, 1970. A study of exhaust emissions from reciprocating aircraft power plants. Environmental Protection Agency, Ann Arbor, Michigan.
- Settimo, G., Manigrasso, M., Avino, P., 2020. Indoor Air Quality: A Focus on the European Legislation and State-of-the-Art Research in Italy. *Atmosphere* 11, 370. <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos11040370>
- Sgro, L.A., Barone, A.C., Commodo, M., D’Alessio, A., De Filippo, A., Lanzuolo, G., Minutolo, P., 2009. Measurement of nanoparticles of organic carbon in non-sooting flame conditions. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 32 I, 689–696. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2008.06.216>
- Skidmore, F.W., 1986. Smoke emission tests on series II and series III Allison T56 turboprop engines. Aeronautical research laboratories Melbourne.
- Şöhret, Y., Kincay, O., Karakoç, T.H., 2015. Combustion efficiency analysis and key emission parameters of a turboprop engine at various loads. *Journal of the Energy Institute* 88, 490–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joei.2014.09.010>
- Spicer, C.W., Holdren, M.W., Cowen, K.A., Joseph, D.W., Satola, J., Goodwin, B., Mayfield, H., Laskin, A., Lizabeth Alexander, M., Ortega, J.V., Newburn, M., Kagann, R., Hashmonay, R., 2009. Rapid measurement of emissions from military aircraft turbine engines by downstream extractive sampling of aircraft on the ground: Results for C-130 and F-15 aircraft. *Atmospheric Environment* 43, 2612–2622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2009.02.012>
- Spicer, C.W., Holdren, M.W., D. L. Smith, D.P. Hughes, M. D. Smith, 1992. Chemical composition of exhaust from aircraft turbine engines. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 111–117.
- Spicer, C.W., Holdren, M.W., Miller, S.E., D. L. Smith, R.N. Smith, Kuhlman, M.R., D.P. Hughes, 1987. Aircraft emissions characterization: TF41-A2, TF30-P103, and TF30-P109 engines. U.S. Air Force, Engineering and Services Laboratory, Tyndall Air Force Base, FL.
- Spicer, C.W., Holdren, M.W., Smith, D.L., Miller, S.E., Smith, R.N., Hughes, D.P., 1989. Aircraft Emissions Characterization: F100 and F110 Engines. Tyndall AFB, FL.
- Stacey, B., Harrison, R.M., Pope, F., 2020. Evaluation of ultrafine particle concentrations and size distributions at London Heathrow Airport. *Atmospheric Environment* 222, 117148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.117148>
- Stettler, M.E.J., Eastham, S., Barrett, S.R.H., 2011. Air quality and public health impacts of UK airports. Part I: Emissions. *Atmospheric Environment* 45, 5415–5424. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2011.07.012>
- Stickles, R., Barrett, J., 2014. TAPS II Combustor Final Report. U.S. Department of Transportation - Federal Aviation Administration.
- Teoh, R., Stettler, M.E.J., Majumdar, A., Schumann, U., Graves, B., Boies, A.M., 2019. A methodology to relate black carbon particle number and mass emissions. *Journal of Aerosol Science* 132, 44–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaerosci.2019.03.006>

- Timko, M.T., Fortner, E., Franklin, J., Yu, Z., Wong, H.-W., Onasch, T.B., Miake-Lye, R.C., Herndon, S.C., 2013. Atmospheric Measurements of the Physical Evolution of Aircraft Exhaust Plumes. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47, 3513–3520. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es304349c>
- UN, 2015. Take Action for the Sustainable Development Goals. United Nations Sustainable Development. URL <https://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/> (accessed 9.5.21).
- US EPA, 1978. Air pollutant emission factors for military and civil aircraft. US EPA.
- Vaught, J.M., Johnson, S.E.J., Parks, W.M., Johnson, R.L., 1971. Final technical report collection and assessment of aircraft emissions base-line data: Turboprop engines (Allison T56-A-15). Report, Environmental Protection Agency, Office Air Programs, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA.
- Vennam, L.P., Vizuete, W., Talgo, K., Omary, M., Binkowski, F.S., Xing, J., Mathur, R., Arunachalam, S., 2017. Modeled Full-Flight Aircraft Emissions Impacts on Air Quality and Their Sensitivity to Grid Resolution: Aircraft Emissions Impacts on Surface AQ. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* 122, 13,472–13,494. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2017JD026598>
- Wang, H., 2010. Formation of nascent soot and other condensed-phase materials in flames. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute.* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2010.09.009>
- Wang, H., Du, D.X., Sung, C.J., Law, C.K., 1996. Experiments and numerical simulation on soot formation in opposed-jet ethylene diffusion flames. *Symposium (International) on Combustion* 26, 2359–2368. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784\(96\)80065-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0082-0784(96)80065-8)
- Wang, H., Frenklach, M., 1997. A detailed kinetic modeling study of aromatics formation in laminar premixed acetylene and ethylene flames. *Combustion and Flame* 110, 173–221. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180\(97\)00068-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0010-2180(97)00068-0)
- Watterson, J., Walker, C., Eggleston, S., 2004. Revision to the method of estimating emissions from aircraft for the UK greenhouse gas inventory. Global Atmosphere Division, DEFRA.
- Wayson, R.L., Fleming, G.G., Iovinelli, R., 2009. Methodology to Estimate Particulate Matter Emissions from Certified Commercial Aircraft Engines. *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association* 59, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.3155/1047-3289.59.1.91>
- Whitt, D.B., Jacobson, M.Z., Wilkerson, J.T., Naiman, A.D., Lele, S.K., 2011. Vertical mixing of commercial aviation emissions from cruise altitude to the surface. *J. Geophys. Res.* 116, D14109. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010JD015532>
- WHO (Ed.), 2021. Global air quality guidelines: particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. WHO, Geneva.
- WHO (Ed.), 2010. Guidelines for indoor air quality: selected pollutants. WHO, Copenhagen.
- Wilcox, L.J., Shine, K.P., Hoskins, B.J., 2012. Radiative forcing due to aviation water vapour emissions. *Atmospheric Environment* 63, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2012.08.072>
- Wilkerson, J.T., Jacobson, M.Z., Malwitz, A., Balasubramanian, S., Wayson, R., Fleming, G., Naiman, A.D., Lele, S.K., 2010. Analysis of emission data from global commercial aviation: 2004 and 2006. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 10, 6391–6408. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-10-6391-2010>
- Winther, M., Kousgaard, U., Ellermann, T., Massling, A., Nøjgaard, J.K., Ketzel, M., 2015. Emissions of NO_x, particle mass and particle numbers from aircraft main engines,

- APU's and handling equipment at Copenhagen Airport. *Atmospheric Environment* 100, 218–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2014.10.045>
- Wong, H.-W., Jun, M., Peck, J., Waitz, I.A., Miake-Lye, R.C., 2015. Roles of Organic Emissions in the Formation of Near Field Aircraft-Emitted Volatile Particulate Matter: A Kinetic Microphysical Modeling Study. *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power* 137, 072606. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4029366>
- Wong, H.-W., Jun, M., Peck, J., Waitz, I.A., Miake-Lye, R.C., 2014. Detailed Microphysical Modeling of the Formation of Organic and Sulfuric Acid Coatings on Aircraft Emitted Soot Particles in the Near Field. *Aerosol Science and Technology* 48, 981–995. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02786826.2014.953243>
- Yacovitch, T.I., Yu, Z., Herndon, S.C., Miake-Lye, R., Liscinsky, D., Knighton, W.B., Kenney, M., Schoonard, C., Pringle, P., 2016. Exhaust Emissions from In-Use General Aviation Aircraft. Transportation Research Board, Washington, D.C. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24612>
- Yim, S.H.L., Lee, G.L., Lee, I.H., Allroggen, F., Ashok, A., Caiazza, F., Eastham, S.D., Malina, R., Barrett, S.R.H., 2015. Global, regional and local health impacts of civil aviation emissions. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 10, 034001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/10/3/034001>
- Yu, F., Turco, R.P., 1997. The role of ions in the formation and evolution of particles in aircraft plumes. *Geophysical Research Letters* 24, 1927–1930. <https://doi.org/10.1029/97GL01822>
- Yu, Z., Timko, M.T., Herndon, S.C., Miake-Lye, R., C., Beyersdorf, A.J., Ziemba, L.D., Winstead, E.L., Anderson, B.E., 2019. Mode-specific, semi-volatile chemical composition of particulate matter emissions from a commercial gas turbine aircraft engine. *Atmospheric Environment* 218, 116974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2019.116974>
- Zanni, S., Lalli, F., Foschi, E., Bonoli, A., Mantecchini, L., 2018. Indoor Air Quality Real-Time Monitoring in Airport Terminal Areas: An Opportunity for Sustainable Management of Micro-Climatic Parameters. *Sensors* 18, 3798. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18113798>
- Zhao, B., Uchikawa, K., Wang, H., 2007. A comparative study of nanoparticles in premixed flames by scanning mobility particle sizer, small angle neutron scattering, and transmission electron microscopy. *Proceedings of the Combustion Institute* 31 I, 851–860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proci.2006.08.064>
- Zurich Airport, 2019. Ultrafine Particle Concentrations Airside Center Zurich Airport.

